

CATALISI

Catalysation of institutional transformations
of Higher Education Institutions through
the adoption of acceleration services

D4.2 MONITORING AND IMPLEMENTATION REPORT (INCLUDING IMPACT ASSESSMENT TOOLKIT)

31/12/2025

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01

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Abstract	Deliverable 4.2, titled "Monitoring and Implementation Report (Including Impact Assessment Toolkit)" constitutes the final evaluation and impact assessment report to assess whether, and/or to what degree, the activities outlined in the action plans have been implemented. The aim of this report is to assess the progress of the participating HEI's in relation to institutional change, provide HEI's with a monitoring support toolkit to self-assess their progress towards organizational change, understand the implementation process of

	<p>institutional changes in implementing HEI's interventions and the role of the acceleration services in driving the HEIs' institutional transformation and assess the effectiveness of the overall project to inform the Policy Recommendations. The report begins from where Deliverable 4.1 (Impact and Evaluation Assessment Plan) left off. After briefly describing the methodology of the approach as per D4.1, D4.2 describes the concrete way in which the evaluation process unfolded, informed by the theories and methodologies outlined previously. This report then analyses the seven case-studies which were produced from the formative evaluation work, the summative evaluation results, followed by a conclusion. This report contains also a Toolkit element, with both a descriptive and prescriptive element, to inform the CATALISI partners, as well as any other HEI, on how to reproduce the methodology and evaluation process herein.</p>
Keywords	<p>Monitoring, Evaluation, Impact, Outcome, Output, Assessment, Formative, Summative, Toolkit, Analysis, Qualitative, Quantitative, Report, Instrument, Tools, Surveys, Interviews, Opinions, Recommendations, Policy.</p>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 4.2 titled “Monitoring and Implementation Report (including impact assessment toolkit)” of the CATALISI initiative (Grant Agreement no. 101094917) aims at assessing “whether, and/or to what degree, the activities outlined in the action plans have been implemented”. The aim of this report is to:

- Assess the progress of the participating HEI's in relation to institutional change.
- Provide HEI's with a monitoring support toolkit to self-assess and qualitatively and quantitatively assure their progress towards organizational change.
- Understand the implementation process of institutional changes in implementing HEI's interventions and the role of the acceleration services in driving the HEI's sustainable institutional transformation.
- Assess the effectiveness of the overall project to inform the Policy Recommendations.

UCC's approach involved a Theory of Change approach, consisting of a formative and summative modality conducted in real-time, throughout the project, to follow the implementing partners in their institutional transformation, thus ensuring constant monitoring, and adjusting of the actions. The Theory of Change (ToC) methodology allowed implementers to identify long-term impacts, and map those backwards with the steps, activities and inputs required to bring about the desired changes; it involved working with the HEIs to co-create Strategic Key Performance Indicators that are SMART and bring the HEIs closer to the change that wish to bring about. Finally, the approach involved consistently integrating feedback from the External Acceleration Board as well as the feedback of the partners, while sharing learnings across the HEIs as appropriate. A Summative component allowed for self-evaluation reinforcing implementers focusing on outcomes and impact.

CATALISI's underpinning programme theory posits HEI institutional transformation as a complex process, requiring deep shifts in specified domains encompassing aspects such as governance, culture, research practices, and financial sustainability. The CATALISI model supports HEIs in going through this transformation by offering a range of acceleration services designed to accelerate the process and maximize its impact. It is important to note that CATALISI's approach is iterative and adaptive, allowing for continuous learning and improvement. Its domains and acceleration services are linked, interrelated and mutually reinforcing. It thus provides an exemplar for scaling HEI change through accelerated co-learning, and an empowering discourse of HEI organisational change.

Some key learnings emerged from the formative and summative evaluation process:

- Involving the right people in the change project is vital. A mix of bottom-up and top-down approach with the involvement of senior leadership and decision makers contributed positively to change agendas. Involving stakeholders across the Quadruple Helix (QH) leads to resilient decision making and stronger outcomes. Using existing and new governance structures in the change agenda helps to strategically embed the change post project.
- Getting the right balance between ambition and realism on what can be achieved during the term of the change project is an important consideration. Some of the most advanced outcomes came from universities that had a relatively narrow focus and appeared to be spending time on the right activity. UCC observed that embedding the actions in strategic documents of the university can also be helpful regarding successful delivery.

- Successful utilisation of the acceleration services, for example, in-person Twinning's and Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops contributed in a leading way to change especially when these were well planned. Community of Practice events such as online webinars and presentations should be intrinsically linked to relevant action items relevant to the partners. Similarly, advanced impacts and collaboration on change grew organically from in-person exchanges over virtual.
- Advanced outcomes are achieved through scaling deep not wide. This means leveraging and adding value to existing university priorities and initiatives. Acceleration services work best when they focus on deepening university efforts in strategic areas. Often the timing is right for a particular change item or focus and CATALISI allowed for that to be accelerated and progressed.
- Using the acceleration services as appropriate and embedding these within action plans worked well but this involved a willingness to experiment and learn through doing, especially in the case of Living Labs.
- Pursuing change through ideating, co-creating, acting, and adjusting through ongoing monitoring and evaluation is not the norm in large organisations such as HEI's. Combined with the effective use of a Theory of Change and strategic KPIs (and having clear ownership of the actions within plans) are all common to the universities that were advanced in delivering desired change.

UCC acknowledges the collaboration of all the CATALISI partners in respect of the evaluation approach and indeed the other evaluative work completed by EY, APRE, F6S, ENOLL as part of the other work packages which was considered for this report.

In conclusion, the CATALISI initiative has demonstrated a dynamic model for institutional transformation across the participating HEIs. While some challenges remain in measuring long-term impact and ensuring sustainability, the combined formative and summative analysis reveal a strong commitment to strategic change, stakeholder engagement, and cultural evolution. The findings offer valuable insights for policymakers seeking to support systemic transformation in higher education and research.

CATALISI is a Horizon Europe project aimed at fostering institutional transformations within HEIs by leveraging innovative acceleration services. CATALISI's legacy is a set of actionable, evidence-based recommendations and a replicable framework for institutional transformation. By following these guidelines, HEIs, alliances, and policymakers can enhance research excellence, drive innovation, and contribute to a more inclusive, resilient, and impactful higher education sector in Europe.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contents

List of figures	7
LIST OF TABLES	8
1. Introduction	10
1.1. CATALISI Background and aim	10
1.2. Introduction to Deliverable 4.2	13
2. Methodology	15
2.1. Theory Driven Evaluation	15
2.1.1. Coordinated Approach	16
2.1.2. Source data	17
2.2. Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology in Theory	18
2.2.1. Aspects of the Approach	19
2.2.2. Formative Aspect (Theory of Change)	19
2.2.3. Summative Aspect	21
2.3. Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology in Practice (Toolkit)	21
2.3.1. Step 1: Apply a ToC Approach with Logic Model and ToC Narrative ...	23
2.3.2. Step 2: Use Formative Evaluation Techniques	25
2.3.3. Step 3: Co-creation and Development of Strategic KPIs	29
2.3.4. Step 4: Summative Evaluation Tool	31
2.3.5. Step 5: Develop Monitoring and Evaluation Dashboard	33
2.3.6. Ex-Post Monitoring and Toolkit Conclusions	35
3. Results	36
3.1. Case Studies (7)	36
3.1.1. Case Study 1: KTU	36
3.1.2. Case Study 2: UJI	40
3.1.3. Case Study 3: LUISS	45
3.1.4. Case Study 4: UG	49
3.1.5. Case Study 5: UCC	53
3.1.6. Case Study 6: AUTH	57
3.1.7. Case Study 7: AUMC	61
3.2. Summative Evaluation Results	66
3.2.1. Action plan implementation	66
3.2.2. Key Achievements to Date	67
3.2.3. Embedding Actions	68
3.2.4. HEI Self-Reflection on CATALISI	70
3.2.5. Learnings from CATALISI	70
3.2.6. Unanticipated Opportunities	72
3.2.7. Exploitation and Dissemination	73
3.2.8. Acceleration Services	73
4. Concluding Observations	78
5. References	84

6. Appendix.....	85
Annex A: Introduction to Evaluation and Impact Assessment Process Template ..	85
Annex B: Partner Action Plan Baseline Data Collection Template	86
Annex C: Partner ToC Narrative Template	87
Annex D: Theory of Change Monitoring Framework	88
Annex E: Structured Bilateral Discussion Template.....	89
Annex F: Example of Workshop Co-Creation and Validation Session.....	90
Annex G: Example of Initial Action Plan and KPI Monitoring Tool.....	91
Annex H: Example of Summative Self-Evaluation Survey	92
Annex I: Example of GDPR-Compliant Model Consent Form Template	96
Annex L: Logic Model Template	97

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1: Cause and Effect Relationship in ToC Process</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Figure 2: UCC introductory presentation to ToC and evaluation methodology, May 2024.....</i>	<i>23</i>
<i>Figure 3: Posters and sticky notes to capture discussions during in-person workshops.</i>	<i>26</i>
<i>Figure 4: Internal report on findings following UCC's workshop during General Assembly at AUTH, January 2025.....</i>	<i>27</i>
<i>Figure 5: UCC workshop at General Assembly in AUTH, January 2025.....</i>	<i>28</i>
<i>Figure 6: Example of structured dialogue for the bilateral meetings between UCC and the HEIs</i>	<i>28</i>
<i>Figure 7: SMART KPIs diagram, Fossil Consulting.</i>	<i>30</i>
<i>Figure 8: Homepage of UCC's CATALISI KPI Monitoring Dashboard as per the pre-alpha version.</i>	<i>34</i>
<i>Figure 9: Analytics section of the CATALISI KPI Monitoring Dashboard as per the pre-alpha version.</i>	<i>34</i>
<i>Figure 10: KTU Strategic KPI Tool.....</i>	<i>39</i>
<i>Figure 11: UJI Strategic KPI Tool.....</i>	<i>43</i>
<i>Figure 12: LUISS Strategic KPI Tool.</i>	<i>48</i>

<i>Figure 13: UG Strategic KPI Tool.....</i>	<i>52</i>
<i>Figure 14: UCC Strategic KPI Tool.....</i>	<i>56</i>
<i>Figure 15: AUTH Strategic KPI Tool.....</i>	<i>60</i>
<i>Figure 16: AUMC Strategic KPI Tool.....</i>	<i>64</i>

LIST OF TABLES

<i>Table 1: Triangulation Framework and Key Data Collection Modalities.....</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>Table 2: Triangulation Source Data</i>	<i>18</i>
<i>Table 3: Aspects of Impact Evaluation.....</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Table 4: The Five Steps of Theory of Change as per Deliverable 4.1 of the CATALISI project.....</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Table 5: Timeline and phases of UCC Evaluation and Impact Assessment process, as executed.....</i>	<i>22</i>
<i>Table 6: KTU Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>38</i>
<i>Table 7: UJI Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>43</i>
<i>Table 8: LUISS Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>47</i>
<i>Table 9: UG Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>52</i>
<i>Table 10: UCC Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>55</i>
<i>Table 11: AUTH Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>59</i>
<i>Table 12: AUMC Transformation Focus.....</i>	<i>64</i>
<i>Table 13: Integration of actions and activities by partners, results from UCC survey.</i>	<i>69</i>
<i>Table 14: Support for Action Plan Activities from key actors in HEIs, results from UCC survey.....</i>	<i>69</i>
<i>Table 15: Utilization of each CATALISI Acceleration Services as rated by the partners from 0 to 10. Emerging (0 to 3), Intermediate (4 to 7), Advanced (8 to 10).</i>	<i>75</i>
<i>Table 16: Usefulness of the acceleration services towards supporting the partner's delivery of planned activities through the CATALISI initiative. As rated by the partners from 0 to 10. Emerging (0 to 3), Intermediate (4 to 7), Advanced (8 to 10).</i>	<i>76</i>
<i>Table 17: Acceleration services reproducibility, confidence of partners in reusing acceleration services to support organizational change going forward. As rated by the partners from 0 to 10. Emerging (0 to 3), Intermediate (4 to 7), Advanced (8 to 10).</i>	<i>77</i>

ABBREVIATIONS

D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
T	Task
WP	Work-Package
GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
DC	Dissemination and Communication
LL	Living Labs
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
CoP	Community of Practice
ERA	European Research Area
R&I	Research & Innovation
ToC	Theory of Change
HEI	Higher Education Institution
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QH	Quadruple Helix
KER	Key Exploitable Result
HE	Higher Education

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. CATALISI BACKGROUND AND AIM

The European Commission (EC) sees universities, research and research-based education as crucial catalysts for improved competitiveness of the European Union in the current and future global environment, and a prerequisite for solving societal problems affecting the continent – maintaining a competitive edge for European products and services. Through their interaction, universities and private sector entities (non-academic research institutes, companies etc.) help in circulating knowledge, upskilling talent and promoting societal engagement. This process of interaction takes place and evolves in a model referred to as the “Quadruple Helix” (QH), in which academia, private sector entities, civil society and government share knowledge, expertise and needs to pursue common goals. Recognizing this process of cross-pollination, the EC is promoting a deeper level of cooperation by facilitating transnational commitments in research and innovation between these different parties.

The European Union and member states have taken critical steps to support Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to pursue excellence and greater academic, innovation and research outputs while at the same time keeping a firm eye on societal engagement as mandated in the Pact for Research & Innovation. Action 13 of the European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2022-2024 is directed at empowering “Higher Education Institutions to develop in line with the ERA, and in synergy with the European Education Area”. This action aims at improving European universities’ competitiveness in research and innovation (R&I) by improving capacity and impact of HEI programs and education. At the same time, the EC is aiming to maximize cross-European research structures and programs to improve synergies and investments in R&I initiatives.

[The Horizon Europe Framework Programme](#) targets specifically this objective – that of promoting institutional change in universities, improving research outcomes and capacity, mainstreaming of open-science, strengthening gender equality and promoting research careers – with the use of “Acceleration Services”, these will be further analysed subsequently in this document.

To respond to this objective, The Horizon Europe funded CATALISI project aims to help and support HEIs to successfully implement strategies and individual pathways for institutional transformation through the adoption of acceleration services. The CATALISI model has two building blocks:

- **Facilitators** (APRE, EY, ENoLL, F6S) which support the transformation of Higher Education Institutions through acceleration services, knowledge transfer, and the implementation of co-designed activities.
- **Implementers** (AUTH, KTU, UCC, UG, UJI, Luiss, AUMC) Higher Education Institutions that implement new reforms in their structures as demonstrators of change in specific domains and intervention areas.
- UCC had a dual role both as an implementer of change and facilitator and leader of the evaluation and impact assessment (WP4) activities.

CATALISI Implementers encompass a diverse range of specializations and geographic locations. Each university possesses a distinct profile and operates within a unique local context that shapes their project activities. These HEIs are situated in seven different European countries:

1. Greece (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki),

2. Lithuania (Kaunas University of Technology),
3. Ireland (University College Cork),
4. Poland (University of Gdansk),
5. Spain (Jaume I University),
6. Italy (Luiss Guido Carli University),
7. Netherlands (Amsterdam University Medical Centre).

The CATALISI HEIs have identified 14 key areas of intervention that each of them considers necessary to address today's global challenges in the field of Research and Innovation (R&I). These intervention areas are inserted within 3 main domains which are at the basis of CATALISI's work.

Domains and Intervention Areas:

1. **Research careers and talent support**

Recognition of qualifications & research careers

Reform of research assessment

Digitalization of higher education sector

Talent circulation & mobility

Addressing life-long learning

Strengthening of human capital

Gender equality & inclusiveness

2. **Research modus operandi**

Mainstreaming of open science and digitalization of research

Public engagement & outreach to solve societal challenges

Reinforcing the role of universities in local innovation systems

Sharing of infrastructure and capacities

3. **Sustainable Research and Education**

Sustainability in education & funding

Sustainability in campus operations

Sustainability in research

The CATALISI project aims at facilitating the HEI's implementation of transformational pathways with respective action plans within one or more of the intervention areas, through the use of 7 innovative and targeted Acceleration Services, listed here below:

1. **Living Labs (LLs):** guided by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), it comprises a participatory and collaborative framework that emphasizes co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and real-world settings for innovation. Living Labs are practical, real-world environments where new ideas and strategies are tested and refined with stakeholders including university staff and students and external partners.

These labs allow for the elaboration of targeted and effective action plans within selected intervention areas.

2. **Counselling:** guided by Ernst & Young (EY), during the development of transformational pathways and action plans, HEIs are guided on specific problems, solvable in short periods of time. Counselling services, including mentoring and coaching, play a crucial role in offering guidance and best practice examples to universities. Moreover, the counselling service is designed as a cross-cutting service for all other acceleration services as it gives constant and accessible guidance throughout the duration of the whole project for all HEIs involved.
3. **Transformational Pathway:** guided by EY, it enhances HEIs' ability to collaborate, innovate, and respond to societal challenges effectively. After the state of affairs assessment of the individual HEI in the LLs environment, a transformational pathway will set an agenda for each HEI to better achieve its institutional transformation and get tangible results at a scheduled time.
4. **Predictive Study on Skills Anticipation:** carried out by EY, it analyzes trends in labor markets to determine which skills will be essential for future workforce needs. A predictive study on skills anticipation can play a crucial role in shaping curriculum development, ensuring that Higher Education Institutions remain responsive to the evolution of key macro-trends, such as environmental, social, political and technological changes. This study helps to foster lifelong learning opportunities and re-skilling and up-skilling for researchers who will be better able to adapt to future challenges.
5. **Community of Practice (CoP):** led by the Agency for the Promotion of European Research (APRE), a collaborative group of experts and practitioners on institutional transformation, formed by Academia and other quadruple helix actors. This service serves as a community where members can collaboratively address challenges, exchange insights on innovation, provide advice and guidance on methodology, and work towards institutional transformations. By connecting with a wide array of stakeholders, the CoPs foster a culture of continuous improvement and support HEIs in better aligning their strategies with regional, national, and European innovation goals.
6. **Capacity Building and Outreach:** carried out by APRE, it provides HEIs with essential methods and skills through onsite exchanges, mutual learning, and tailored webinars. It aims to provide HEIs with methods, skills and capabilities to develop transformation strategies related to specific RRI principles and topics in a participatory way, relying on knowledge sharing, mutual learning, Twinning schemes and tailor-made webinars on specific R&I RRI topics, with a particular focus on Open Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI) principles and practices. With this service, universities can address challenges more effectively by fostering a collaborative environment conducive to meaningful progress and sustainable change in the higher education landscape.
7. **The Catalyst Hub (formerly Marketplace):** lead by F6S Innovation, it is structured into three key areas: Learning, Funding and Collaboration. It aims to facilitate the identification of funding opportunities and collaborations for researchers to increase R&D investments. It fosters stronger connections between academia and industry, helping to bridge the gap between research outputs and market needs.

1.2. INTRODUCTION TO DELIVERABLE 4.2

Deliverable 4.2 titled “Monitoring and Implementation Report (including impact assessment toolkit)” of the CATALISI initiative (Grant Agreement no. 101094917) is described as the deliverable which is tasked with assessing “whether, and/or to what degree, the activities outlined in the action plans have been implemented”. The aim of this report is to:

- Assess the progress of the participating HEI's in relation to institutional change.
- Provide HEI's with a monitoring support toolkit to self-assess and qualitatively and quantitatively assure their progress towards organizational change.
- Understand the implementation process of institutional changes in implementing HEI's interventions and the role of the acceleration services in driving the HEI's sustainable institutional transformation.
- Assess the effectiveness of the overall project to inform the Policy Recommendations.

UCC initially presented its Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan in the *Deliverable 4.1, - Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan*, delivered in April 2024. This document illustrated the planned structure of UCC's plan, explaining the “dual aspect” nature of the approach (Formative and Summative) and the theoretical underpinnings behind the methodology. D4.1 explained the concepts behind the notion of institutional change and its framework, Theory of Change approach as an underpinning to UCC's process, and the expected design, structure and execution of the evaluation approach.

Deliverable 4.2 starts from where 4.1 left off. Following an initial introduction (Chapter 1), D4.2 begins (in Sections 2.1 and 2.2) with a summary overview of the methodology and theoretical underpinning of the evaluation process which are illustrated, in-depth, in D4.1. For a more comprehensive look at the theory behind the approach, the reader is invited to refer to that deliverable.

After explaining the theory behind the methodology, Section 2.3 of this report illustrates the concrete way in which the Evaluation and Impact Assessment process was executed. This portion of the report constitutes also the Toolkit element of this deliverable; the function of this section is to display to the reader the actual way the process was conducted, by looking at the different steps which UCC employed throughout the project. The reader will be able to follow both the chronological succession of the different steps which were conducted in WP4, as well as an in-depth look at each phase, explaining the rationale behind the different phases. In following the 5 steps in Section 2.3, the reader will be presented with a *descriptive* explanation of the process. That said, throughout this section, there will also be *prescriptive* elements to each step, as to explain to a person or institution, wishing to reproduce this methodology, how to undertake the process.

Once Section 2.3 has illustrated the actual execution of UCC's approach from a broad and cross-institutional view, Section 3.1 of this report will illustrate the results stemming from this Evaluation and Impact Assessment process.

Section 3.1 contains the Seven Case Studies which were produced from UCC's work. Each of these sections will follow the process undertaken by each of the implementing partners in co-designing, co-creating and co-managing their respective Action Plans and Transformational Pathways. As the reader will see, throughout the case studies, UCC will apply the theories and methodologies as illustrated in Deliverable 4.1 and Chapter 2 of this report. Each case study contains an overview of the respective HEI, an analysis of their Transformational Pathway, the Theory of Change Narrative stemming from their co-creation process with UCC, the articulation of the HEI's responses to feedback, comments and support

provided by the External Acceleration Board (EAB), facilitating partners and UCC, and finally an overview of the results (outputs and outcomes) and summary observations for each HEI.

Following the Seven Case Studies, Section 2 of Chapter 3 of this report will have an in-depth view of the results from the Ex-Post Summative Self-Assessment Survey conducted by UCC in June of 2025. This survey constitutes the bulk of the summative results stemming from UCC's evaluation work and Section 3.2 will cover all of its findings.

Finally, the Concluding Observations chapter of this report (Chapter 4) will contain overarching conclusions from the CATALISI project, gathering the individual conclusions for each HEI in their respective case study, in a holistic overview of CATALISI.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. THEORY DRIVEN EVALUATION

UCC developed a “theory-driven” Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan, to assess the CATALISI project, which was thoroughly illustrated in Deliverable 4.1; for an in-depth explanation of the theoretical underpinning of the evaluation work, please refer to D4.1.

This ‘complex evaluation’ approach uses the underlying theory of the intervention (in this case CATALISI project) to guide the evaluation and understand the mechanisms that lead to specific outcomes. Importantly, complex intervention research of this nature goes beyond asking whether an intervention works in the sense of achieving its intended outcome—to, and sometimes more crucially, asking a broader range of questions such as identifying what other impact it has, assessing its value relative to the resources required to deliver it, theorising how it works, taking account of how it interacts with the context in which it is implemented, how it contributes to system change, and how the evidence can be used to support real world decision making. Thus, there is a focus on prioritising the usefulness of evaluative insights for decision making in selecting the optimal research perspective and in prioritising answerable research questions.

To deliver solutions for real world Higher Education practice, a complex project such as CATALISI requires an *inductive logic* that asks whether and how the intervention will be feasible, acceptable, implementable, cost effective, scalable, and transferable across contexts. In line with a broader conception of complexity, the scope of complex evaluation research needs to include the development, identification, and evaluation of whole project such as CATALISI and the assessment of how such interventions contribute to higher education system change.

A crucial aspect of evaluation design is the choice of outcome measures or evidence of change and their co-development with stakeholders. UCC in this case worked with each HEI (so called “Implementers” in our project) to assess which outcomes are most important. This included how to deal with multiple outcomes in the analysis with consideration for providing evidence of change. Importantly a focus on outcome measures captures changes to a system rather than changes in individuals. Examples include changes in relationships within an organisation, the introduction of policies, changes in social norms, or normalisation of practice. Such system level outcomes include how changing the dynamics of one part of a system works smartly to influence change in other parts for cumulative impact.

A purely quantitative approach is rarely adequate for complex intervention research, whereas qualitative and mixed methods designs are necessary to answer questions beyond effectiveness. Because effect estimates are often context bound, average effects are not a useful guide to decision makers working in different contexts. Most importantly contextualised understandings of how an intervention induces change might be more useful, as well as details on the most important enablers and constraints on its delivery across a range of settings.

Impact evaluation can answer questions around alignment with the CATALISI model and quality of implementation (e.g. what is implemented and how?), mechanisms of change (e.g., how does the delivered intervention produce change?), and context (e.g., how does local context affect implementation and outcomes?). The evaluation can help determine why an intervention lags in some contexts or has unanticipated consequences, or why it works and how it can be optimised. Such findings can facilitate further development of the intervention programme theory. In a theory based or systems evaluation, there is not necessarily such a clear distinction between process and outcome evaluation as there is for example in a more quantitative-focused effectiveness study. The goals are to prioritise theory-building through,

for instance, the use of a case study to understand how outcomes or system behaviour are generated through interventions such as CATALISI.

2.1.1. Coordinated Approach

UCC integrated its approach, where feasible, with other monitoring and evaluation tasks delivered by the facilitators ENoLL, APRE and EY. This alignment was critical not to overwhelm the Implementers with overlapping and burdensome reporting requirements. This form of coordination is an important element of complex evaluation research.

This strategy involves using multiple data sources, methods, theories, and/or investigators to study the same phenomenon from different angles. The primary purpose is to enhance the credibility, validity, and depth of research findings by counteracting the inherent biases or limitations of a single approach. Different data collection methods (often combining qualitative and quantitative approaches) and involving multiple researchers, observers, or analysts in the study helps to reduce individual bias and ensure a more objective interpretation of the data. Theoretical flexibility helps researchers also avoid being overly influenced by a single perspective and remain open exploring alternative explanations. The benefits are:

- **Enhancing Validity and Credibility:** By cross-checking evidence from different sources or methods, evaluations can increase confidence that the findings reflect reality.
- **Reducing Bias:** Utilizing multiple data sources helps to minimize the influence of individual or methodological bias.
- **Gaining Comprehensive Understanding:** uncovering nuanced insights and complexities that might be overlooked with a single method, providing a richer, more holistic view of activities.
- **Strengthen Findings:** Assembling data from different approaches ensures results are strengthened.

Key Data Collection Modalities	
Theory of Change Workshops and Bilateral Meetings	Summative Survey
EAB Reports	Document Analysis e.g. reporting templates from MMLs and Twinning etc.
Baseline Data (Needs Assessment and Action Plans)	Validation Workshops and Co-Analysis Process

TABLE 1: TRIANGULATION FRAMEWORK AND KEY DATA COLLECTION MODALITIES

A central aspect of the coordinated approach entailed close collaboration with the CATALISI External Acceleration Board (EAB). This is a group of *external experts in institutional transformation within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)* who were responsible for evaluating the seven transformational pathways implemented by the project.

Key details about the EAB and its role in the CATALISI project include:

- **Evaluation Process:** The EAB was part of a collective evaluation process that assesses the effectiveness of the tailored acceleration services designed to foster Research & Innovation (R&I) reforms.
- **Function:** The EAB provided expert guidance, evaluation, and feedback on the institutional changes implemented by the seven Implementers (partner universities).
- **Facilitation:** The EAB worked alongside UCC, APRE, EY, ENoLL, and F6S—who supported the transformation journey through knowledge transfer and co-designed activities.

The EAB helped to ensure that the methodologies applied by the universities were effective, sustainable, and aligned with the project's goals of fostering change in governance and research strategies. The EAB was provided with evaluation sheets and evaluation questions to guide their reviews and they were asked to focus on aspects such as quality and pertinence of the Transformation Pathways (see definition below) consistency feasibility of the goals and actions, timeframe and sustainability, improvements /recommendations and suggestions. Each round involved 4 personal remote individual evaluations and a summary evaluation from all members.

An additional key aspect of the coordinated approach was close synchronicity with the Transformational Pathways and Action Plans to ensure their strategic development through the formative evaluation process and evaluate their effectiveness.

The Transformation Pathway is a long-term, tailored roadmap for an HEI's institutional transformation. It serves as a guide for change, outlining goals, actions, and milestones. These pathways are developed collaboratively with stakeholders through "Living Labs" to assess the current situation, identify needs, and establish strategic objectives. They are integrated into the university's governance, policies, and long-term strategy to ensure sustainable changes. The pathways are considered "living documents" and are updated annually based on progress.

Action Plans are concrete, operational steps derived from the Transformational Pathway. They translate the strategic pathway into measurable progress. Developed using a "Theory of Change" approach, they detail the necessary inputs, outputs, and long-term impacts. Key elements include SMART KPIs, clear goals, and timelines. These plans are co-designed by stakeholders from academia, industry, government, and civil society and are implemented over two main cycles with support services like counselling or mentoring. The Action Plans focus on 14 intervention areas across three main domains:

1. **Research Careers and Talent Support:** Covering areas like research assessment reform and talent mobility.
2. **Research Modus Operandi:** Including open science, digitalization, and public engagement.
3. **Sustainable Research and Education:** Addressing funding and campus sustainability.

2.1.2. Source data

The evaluation and impact assessment plan was complemented by a large and comprehensive set of sources and data inputs which allowed UCC to conduct a thorough review of the Implementers' activities and actions within their Action Plans and Transformational Pathways. The data sets which informed the evaluation and impact assessment can be compiled into several groups, each produced and originating from different processes and sources.

<p><i>Facilitator's deliverables and contributions</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D1.1 Acting-LLs Needs Assessment and 4-Helix Ecosystem by ENoLL • D1.2 Acting-LLs Action Plans by ENoLL • D2.2 Mobilization and Mutual Learning Report by APRE • Task 3.2 Design Lab for Transformational Pathways: Strategy and Agenda Setting (V2.0) by EY • Policy Recommendations by EY • D6.2 First Policy Brief by APRE • D6.3 Final Policy Brief • CATALISI Stories of Transformation Booklet by F6S
<p><i>External Acceleration Board (T.4.6)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First External Acceleration Board Feedback, November 2023 • Second External Acceleration Board Feedback, February 2025 • Final Collective External Acceleration Board Feedback, November 2025
<p><i>University College Cork's formative and summative activities:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First set of bilateral meetings between UCC and implementing partners, 2024 • Workshop on Acceleration Services utilization during the General Assembly at AUTH, January 2025 • Second set of bilateral meetings between UCC and implementing partners, 2025 • Summative Self-evaluation Survey of all CATALISI partners, June 2025

TABLE 2: TRIANGULATION SOURCE DATA

2.2. EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY IN THEORY

This section briefly summarizes the theoretical underpinning of UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment methodology which was amply illustrated in Deliverable 4.1. For a more in-depth description of the theory behind the evaluation, please refer to said document. Deliverable 4.1 (Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan) was developed within the framework of the CATALISI project to outline the theoretical and methodological basis of UCC's evaluation and impact assessment process. The document outlines the concepts behind institutional change, the evaluation methodology and the planned formative and summative aspects of the approach.

2.2.1. Aspects of the Approach

As described in depth in Chapter 3 of D4.1, UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4) approach was built around a "two-part approach" towards the project. WP4 involved a Formative and Summative element to the evaluation.

The Formative aspect (ex-ante) would be undertaken throughout the development and implementation of the different interventions in each HEI's case study. This would provide real-time information to inform the changes and adjustments to activities and indicators.

The Summative aspect (ex-post) would be undertaken towards the end of the project to assess its efficacy.

Formative	Ex-Ante: undertaken during the development and implementation of an intervention. It provides real-time evidence to inform decisions regarding reorienting or making changes and improvements. Qualitative methods using a Theory of Change and outcomes monitoring using co-developed indicators and an indicator dashboard.
Summative	Ex-Post: undertaken near the end of the program or intervention to make judgements about its efficacy. It informs decisions about the potential of replications, scaling up, and provides data-based evidence for policy recommendations. Qualitative methods, including document analysis, interviews, and participant observation.

TABLE 3: ASPECTS OF IMPACT EVALUATION

2.2.2. Formative Aspect (Theory of Change)

The Formative aspect of the evaluation was built around a Theory of Change (ToC) approach, described in section 3.1 of D4.1. A ToC process is a rigorous yet participatory approach in which stakeholders identify and articulate their desired long-term impacts and, 'working backwards' identify short- and medium-term objectives, milestones, inputs and activities to achieve said impact. The delineation of these steps and the connection of the causal links which bind them, produces a ToC Narrative which constitutes a summary of the stakeholder's theory on its pathway to change and contains the assumptions, rationales and interventions behind its logic (Reinholz and Andrews 2020).

FIGURE 1: CAUSE AND EFFECT RELATIONSHIP IN TOC PROCESS

The 5 Steps of ToC
<p>STEP 1: Constructing and adopting a theory of change which helps to identify objectives and challenges, as well as outlining the process and actions for achieving the intended outcomes and impacts.</p>
<p>STEP 2: Developing a results chain to outline the theory of change – this covers both the implementation process and the results outcomes.</p>
<p>STEP 3: Specifying the evaluation question(s) with a focus on impact or the changes directly attributable to an intervention, providing also a narrative context to the theory of change to orient the choice of appropriate indicators.</p>
<p>STEP 4: Selecting indicators to allow for gathering of data that answer the evaluation question(s) and that allow the assessment of performance and process.</p>
<p>STEP 5: Implementing the TOC process, evaluating positive/negative features of impacts related to the different challenges, analysing and interpreting the findings.</p>

TABLE 4: THE FIVE STEPS OF THEORY OF CHANGE AS PER DELIVERABLE 4.1 OF THE CATALISI PROJECT

The monitoring element of the Formative Evaluation, as described in section 3.1.3 of Deliverable 4.1, involves the identification of baseline data and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), conducting meetings with the implementing partners to sense-check the implementations and, finally, providing tools and a dashboard to help the HEIs monitor their progress:

Baseline Data: Initial stock-taking (as per Section 3.1.3 of Deliverable 4.1), in conjunction with WP1, to identifying the HEI's needs and priorities in relation to the intervention areas and analysis of the context/stakeholders to conduct institutional changes in R&I based on analysis of actual needs of their respective organisations and the feasibility of applying interventions in their specific local contexts. Furthermore, in conjunction with WP3 (T 3.3. Predictive Study) this would provide the basis for a comparative analysis between the initial state conditions of each HEI.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): process of identification and co-creation of KPIs for each HEI to ensure accurate and impactful monitoring of the activities in each partner's intervention areas. The identification of the KPIs would follow the SMART guidelines (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Time-based).

Meetings: a series of recurrent online meetings (bilateral meetings) held between UCC and each implementing partner, throughout the project implementation, to continuously monitor, assess and sense-check the state of each HEI's intervention through the use of questions and guided discussions (in-depth descriptions of these structured dialogues, including templates, can be found in section 2.3).

Monitoring Dashboard and Tools: the HEIs provided with a set of tools to aid in the monitoring of their interventions, including a dashboard for the visualization and tracking of predominantly quantitative indicators.

2.2.3. Summative Aspect

Section 3.2 of Deliverable 4.1 describes the theory behind the summative aspect of the evaluation. This aspect, conducted towards the end of the project, and structured as to assess the efficacy of the initiative, entails:

- The collection of relevant documents (including deliverables, tasks and transformational pathways) produced throughout the project for analysis.
- Collection of participant observations.
- Structuring of final case studies (Section 3.1 of this report).
- Final data analysis.

2.3. EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY IN PRACTICE (TOOLKIT)

Now that Section 2.2 has described, in a summary form, the theory behind UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan, as described in Deliverable 4.1, Section 2.3 of this report will illustrate in what way that plan was concretely carried out, by describing the process UCC went through in conducting both the Formative, as well as the Summative, aspects of the evaluation. As the reader will see throughout this section, the actual execution of the evaluation followed closely the plan as described in D4.1. That said, certain adaptations and changes were made throughout the project, which will be explained throughout.

This section, although describing in what way the evaluation and impact assessment was structured and conducted, comprises the basis of the Toolkit also present, in its condensed form, at the end of each step. The Toolkit needs to be seen as both a guidebook for any institution which seeks to reproduce UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment process, as well as for the CATALISI implementing partners to better understand the framework of the evaluation and provide guidance for future creation and monitoring of the transformations which were initiated in the project.

As we will see throughout the following sections, the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Steps contain both a **descriptive** as well as a **prescriptive** element. Every step illustrates, in detail, the process undertaken by UCC, the Implementers and Facilitators, in operationalizing the theory described in Deliverable 4.1, by describing the timelines and the concrete executions of the steps, followed by their outcomes; this constitutes the descriptive element. The prescriptive aspect, contained in the "Toolkit Step" sections at the end of each section, explains in simple yet comprehensive terms *how* to apply the methodology. This last section, as mentioned before, is specifically aimed towards institutions who want to replicate the process or CATALISI partners wishing to have a streamlined description of what occurred throughout the project. Furthermore, in the Toolkit Steps, the reader will be guided through the ample annex section, which can be found at the end of this report, which contains material, examples and templates to aid in the duplication of the process.

UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment process followed the structure and timeline as described in the below table. The first round of evaluation was entirely formative, involving the introduction of the ToC process, the evaluation process, and a first set of bilateral meetings, online workshops with the interested stakeholders and the gathering and integration of the Evaluation Acceleration Board (EAB) feedback (led by APRE). The process also included validation of results by the partners at an in-person workshop. These produced a first structured draft of each HEI's Action Plans and Transformational Pathways, respectively conducted by ENoLL and EY as tasks leaders of these activities.

Round 2 of the evaluation included a second set of bilateral meetings and EAB feedback to finetune the actions and activities, and the selection of the final KPIs. The second round terminated with the initiation of the summative aspect of the evaluation, which was structured in a self-assessment survey to evaluate, ex-post, the outcomes, outputs, impacts, opinions, experiences etc. stemming from the CATALISI project. Again, the results were validated with all partners at an in-person workshop. By the end of this round, the Action Plans and Transformational Pathways were mostly in their final form.

Lastly, the final round of the evaluation involved the integration of the 3rd round of EAB feedback, the analysis of the formative and summative data collected hitherto, the initial drafting of an internal qualitative and quantitative report, the sharing of the findings with the other partners, the structuring of the final evaluation report, and the sense-checking of the results with the partners in a final validation workshop.

Timeline and Phases of UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment Process	
Round 1 Evaluation (Formative)	Stock-taking of HEI baseline conditions by ENoLL and EY (March/October 2023) M3-M10
	1 st Round EAB Feedback by APRE (November 2023) M11
	Introduction to Evaluation Approach (May 2024) M17
	Follow-up ToC Workshop (September 2024) M21
	1 st Phase Bilateral with each Implementer (November 2024) M23
	Validation Workshop and Report from GA in AUTH (January 2025) M25
Round 2 Evaluation (Formative & Summative)	2 nd Round EAB Feedback by APRE (February 2025) M27
	2 nd Phase Bilateral with each Implementer (April/June 2025) M28-M30
	Summative Self-Assessment Survey (June 2025) M30
	Strategic KPI development (July 2025) M31
Draft Evaluation Report (Summative)	Analysis of Data (August 2025) M32
	Internal Qualitative and Quantitative Report (September 2025) M33
	3 rd round of EAB Feedback, by APRE (November 2025) M35
	Final Evaluation Report (October/December 2025) M34-M36
	Validation Workshop at GA in Amsterdam (November 2025) M35

TABLE 5: TIMELINE AND PHASES OF UCC EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT PROCESS, AS EXECUTED.

The table above follows a roughly chronological illustration of the different steps undertaken throughout the evaluation. That said, as evident in the table, there is some overlap between different steps which might have occurred before or during other activities which are listed further down in the table. Sections 2.3.1 to 2.3.6 of the report will cover these different steps in more detail, not chronologically, but logically, to describe the rationale behind their execution, and their interconnectedness with other phases which preceded or succeeded them.

The results section (Chapter 3 onwards) of this report will cover each HEI's case study, and the reader will be able to witness how this methodology was applied on a case-by-case basis with each implementing partner, providing the practical examples and application of the methodology.

2.3.1. Step 1: Apply a ToC Approach with Logic Model and ToC Narrative

The first step in UCC's evaluation process began with an introduction to the Theory of Change process to the different partners. This presentation, conducted in the form of a webinar in May 2024, concentrated on the theories behind institutional change, the proposed plan by UCC for evaluation as per Deliverable 4.1, and the evaluation methodology of WP4. In the presentation, UCC introduced the partners to the Logic Model, the Theory of Change methodology and the concepts behind the Impact Focus of the approach, concentrating particularly on the selection of Strategic and highly impactful KPIs.

FIGURE 2: UCC INTRODUCTORY PRESENTATION TO TOC AND EVALUATION METHODOLOGY, MAY 2024.

The introduction to UCC's approach had been preceded by a **first-round of feedback by the External Acceleration Board**, structured and guided by APRE as task leader of this activity, **on each of the HEIs in November 2023**. The EAB was provided with evaluation sheets and evaluation questions to guide their revisions. This included aspects such as quality and pertinence of the pathway, consistency feasibility of the goals and actions, timeframe and sustainability, improvements/recommendations and suggestions. Each round involved 4 personal remote individual evaluations and a summary evaluation from all members.

The first round of feedback by the EAB was heavily reliant on the work conducted by **ENOLL** and **EY**, respectively in their **Task 1.1 and 1.2**, on Acting LLs, and **Task 3.2** on the partner's transformational pathways. T1.1 involved an in-depth analysis of each of the seven Implementers to explore and assess the local context, barriers and framework conditions that could influence the respective institutional transformation. This was further complemented

by a stakeholder mapping by each of the Implementing partners, also with the help of ENoLL. ENoLL conducted several **workshops** for this purpose, which resulted in 153 participants attending four workshops organised in real-life setting at Implementers' sites, two hybrid workshops with participants both at Implementers' sites and online, and one workshop fully organised online.

The primary methodologies used here involved UCC's use of the EAB evaluation sheets applied consistently to structured dialogue sessions. These helped guide the revision from a quality and pertinence of the pathway perspective but also from a consistency of approach, feasibility, timeframe, sustainability, feedback and enhancement perspective. The vehicle used was bespoke evaluation sessions which took place remotely (or in person on the back of other CATALISI events) as well as a group evaluation session.

UCC and ENoLL, as leaders of respectively WP4 and 1, conducted an initial stock-taking with each of the HEIs to aid in the development of an initial baseline set of data for each implementer. Through this process, CATALISI identified and assessed local initial conditions, context barriers and framework conditions which could affect the institutional transformations of the HEIs under the different domain intervention areas (as per Task 1.1 and 1.2). This was accompanied by the aforementioned ENoLL workshops which included 153 Quadruple Helix participants, and a SWOT analysis of the partners planned interventions. The McKinsey 7-S framework and a PESTLE analysis were employed to capture the current state of the HEIs and assess conditions affecting each of the institution's transformational plans (for further information on McKinsey 7-S and PESTLE analyses, please refer to section 3.1.3 of Deliverable 4.1).

Task 3.2 by EY aimed at defining the methodology that was used to build tailored transformational pathways for each HEI. This task produced an analysis of the intervention areas which each implementing partner had decided to concentrate on, identifying the methodology, risks and mitigating measures employed in the creation of each of the Implementers' transformational pathways and related actions/activities.

These two key contributions (ENoLL's Task 1.1 and 1.2 and EY's Task 3.2) fed into the EAB's first feedback. The external evaluators were complimentary of the high level of ambition which was showcased by the HEIs in the selection of their intervention areas, goals and scopes. That said, the evaluators also noted that in some cases, the eagerness of the implementing partners were producing perhaps too ambitious plans which would lead to unfeasibility and risk when it came to certain partners. Overall, the EAB's first round of feedback underlined:

- The struggle between Ambition vs Realism,
- Need for clearer KPIs,
- Need for a more focused approach and set of actions/activities in the Action Plans and Transformational Pathways.

The activities conducted and the feedback submitted hitherto, allowed the establishment of a **baseline set of data, ToC Narrative** and the first draft of the Action Plans and Transformational Pathways, for each HEI, on which the subsequent phases of the Formative Evaluation were built, and which guided the partners in their interventions.

Toolkit Step 1

1. Introduce partners to Theory of Change Approach and Evaluation & Impact Assessment Methodology for the project (*template of Introduction in Annex A*).
2. Integrate other partners' contributions relating to:
 - a. Initial conditions,
 - b. selected domains and intervention areas,
 - c. desired impacts and outcomes,
 - d. SWOT analyses,
 - e. barriers and enablers.
3. Receive first round of feedback by External Acceleration Board in relation to initial conditions and objectives.
4. Produce Action Plan Draft with Baseline Data Set and ToC Narrative (*template and examples in Annex B and C*). The ToC Narrative for each partner can be operationalized further through the use of a ToC Monitoring Framework Table (*template in Annex D*).

2.3.2. Step 2: Use Formative Evaluation Techniques

The Formative element constituted the unique aspect of UCC's approach to the evaluation. As described earlier in this report and in Deliverable 4.1: while most Evaluation and Impact Assessments revolve around the initial establishment of the opening conditions and baseline data, the execution of the project, and a final ex-post summative evaluation of the results, UCC's approach envisioned a Formative component, which would be continuous throughout the project, in real-time, supportive and provide coaching to the Implementers. This would structure the interventions, actions, activities, and related elements, in the form of a "living document", which would be constantly sense-checked by the HEIs, with the help of UCC, and fine-tuned as the project evolved. Furthermore, the Formative component of the evaluation would concentrate especially on the outcomes and impacts of the project, and constantly integrate the EAB's feedback as it came in.

The tools used in the Formative aspect were primarily organized in the form of structured bilateral questions/discussions with each implementing partner, and validation workshops to sense-check the results and progress of their work. These were integrated and supplemented, throughout the Formative aspect of the evaluation, by the EAB's rounds of feedback submitted to the CATALISI project in November 2023, February and November 2025.

The **1st Phase Bilateral** discussions between UCC and each HEI were conducted in November 2024. These discussions were heavily reliant on the Task 3.2 conducted by EY on each of the HEI's Transformational Pathways, the Deliverables 1.1 and 1.2 by ENoLL on the Acting LLs Action Plans, and the EAB's first round of feedback. The bilateral meetings discussed the target intervention areas and goal overviews, each of the external advisor's comments (with an intent to address and incorporate them), the clarity and pertinence of each HEI's objectives, and the consistency, correctness, feasibility and achievability of said goals. Finally, each bilateral concluded with a discussion on the improvement suggestions by the EAB and strategizing on how to integrate them. The first set of bilateral meetings were then used by the HEI's to further fine-tune their work.

Around the same time as the first set of bilateral discussions, a **follow-up workshop was conducted by UCC, in September 2024, on the ToC approach** with the implementing partners. This workshop, which was conducted approximately five months after the first introduction to ToC, and the initial drafting of the HEI's Action Plans and Transformational

Pathways, was meant to strengthen the Implementers' appreciation for the approach, especially following the integration of the EAB's first set of comments, and to ensure that the implementing partners were correctly exploiting the instruments and methods provided by the Acceleration Services. Beyond that UCC was keen to ensure that the acceleration services were embedded in the action plans. This session was used by the Facilitators to better showcase how their services might help the HEI's in their implementation. Furthermore, the workshop exposed a relative low level of engagement with certain Acceleration Services up to this point; an aspect which would become central in the subsequent phases of the Formative process.

FIGURE 3: POSTERS AND STICKY NOTES TO CAPTURE DISCUSSIONS DURING IN-PERSON WORKSHOPS.

In **January 2025, during the General Assembly hosted by AUTH in Thessaloniki**, UCC had the opportunity to conduct another **workshop**, this time in person, specifically meant to validate the work so far conducted in the Formative process and assess the utilization of the Acceleration Services by the implementing partners, through the use of a SWOT analysis. This helped identify potential areas for continuous improvement and mapped the CATALISI partner solutions to the challenges. Out of the multiple recommendations which stemmed from this workshop (all contained in an internal report which was written after the event), the most important outcomes were:

- The need to reduce the jargon-heavy descriptions of the Acceleration Services and define more concrete, result-driven outcomes for each,
- An overlap between several services was noted (specifically the Catalyst Hub, Counselling and CoP),
- Need for the integration of senior level decision makers in the Reinforce Human Capital service.

FIGURE 4: INTERNAL REPORT ON FINDINGS FOLLOWING UCC'S WORKSHOP DURING GENERAL ASSEMBLY AT AUTH, JANUARY 2025.

Following the work conducted by the implementing partners which integrated the first set of EAB recommendations, follow-up workshops on Acceleration Services and ToC process, and the first bilateral meetings between UCC and the HEIs, this information was compiled and delivered to the EAB, in the form of the updated action plans, at the end of 2024, for a **second set of feedback, which was submitted to CATALISI in February 2025**. As the feedback exposed, the EAB was pleased to find that UCC had operationalized the EAB comments into the implementer's actions and that the HEIs had integrated much of the comments of the first feedback round, streamlining their focus and Action Plans, improving alignment with institutional strategies, increased use of co-creation processes. That said, the EAB also noted the relative lack of interaction beyond the respective institutions, of academic field, to encompass a truly Quadruple Helix interaction with external stakeholders. Furthermore, out of the multiple recommendations, the EAB stressed:

- The need for clear and impactful KPIs,
- The need to pursue long-term and strategic impact with strategies for institutionalization,
- Stronger stakeholder involvement,
- Pursuing collaborative learning, both inter- and intra-institutional.

FIGURE 5: UCC WORKSHOP AT GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN AUTH, JANUARY 2025.

The second set of EAB recommendations were followed, shortly after, by **the 2nd Phase Bilateral** meetings between UCC and the HEIs, to address these comments and further strengthen their respective interventions. These bilateral meetings were conducted between April and May 2025 and, just as in the case of the first set of bilateral meetings, followed a structured dialogue framework (example template in Annex E) to standardize the discussions and guide the conversation. In the case of the second set of bilateral meetings, the discussion points were centred around the Transformational Pathways and Action Plans, potential supported needed by the HEIs for long-term institutional integration, engagement with acceleration services and progress towards exploitation and dissemination activities. This last point was conceived as an aid towards F6S's work in WP5 and the results were fed into its activities. Throughout the bilateral meetings, UCC gained a deep appreciation of the transformational pathways being pursued by each implementing partners and the activities in their action plans. UCC's considerations and recommendations stemmed from both the Team's evaluation of the Implementer's activities as well as integrating the EAB's comments whenever possible.

UCC
University College Cork, Ireland
Coláiste na hOileánuí Corcaigh

CATALISI

UCC Bilateral Action Plan Overview

UCC Action Plan: [CATALISI Action Plan UCC.xlsx](#)

Date/time: July 4th, 2025 @ 13:00 (CET)

Participants: Martin Galvin, David Hogan, David O'Connell, Matteo Pallocca

Meeting Discussion

1. Transformation Pathway and Updated Actions:
2. Potential support needed towards embedding actions within your institution long-term:
3. Engagement with Acceleration Services and embedding them in your institution for long-term implementation and utilization:
4. Progress towards dissemination and Key Exploitable Results:

FIGURE 6: EXAMPLE OF STRUCTURED DIALOGUE FOR THE BILATERAL MEETINGS BETWEEN UCC AND THE HEIS

The **final round of EAB feedback** was submitted to CATALISI in November of 2025, based on the updated and final version of the HEIs' Transformational Pathways. Overall, the feedback reiterated the same recommendations and comments present in previous EAB reports and noticed an increased confidence in iterative learning and institutional alignment, strengthened internal co-creation and sharper strategic plans. The EAB also noted continued

room for expanding cross-partner exchange, external stakeholder engagement, more focused KPIs, but also the difficulties in ensuring long-term institutional change which is sustainable and measurable beyond the time constraints of the CATALISI project.

Another important element of the Formative (and later Summative) Evaluation, which was vital and which was conducted throughout the entire 36-month long project, was comprised of the monthly meetings, organized and led by APRE, which allowed UCC, as well as the other facilitating and implementing partners, to constantly sense-check the progress of their work. Although not initially envisioned as an integral part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment methodology, these meetings aided in the coordination and cross-pollination of data and insight between the partners and, although difficult to monitor or quantify, provided an extra element of communication and coordination for the evaluation.

As the final step of the Formative aspect of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment process, UCC conducted a validation workshop during the final, in person general assembly in November 2025 in Amsterdam, to sense-check the results of the work conducted until then through a participatory evaluation methodology. This event was also used to evaluate the Summative results of the evaluation and was an integral part of the validation process to analyse the data produced throughout the process and the creation process for this report.

Toolkit Step 2

1. Co-design and co-create Formative Evaluation Tools and Techniques:
 - a. Structured bilateral discussions between the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Leader and the Partners (*template of structured bilateral discussion in Annex E*).
 - b. Co-creation Workshops to validate progress of interventions (*example of workshop board in Annex F*).
2. Repeat the Formative Evaluation Tools throughout the project as many times as necessary to support the Partner in its co-creation of actions, activities and indicators.
3. Integrate EAB's comments and feedback on Partner's interventions throughout the Formative process.
4. Utilize other structured dialogues and meetings in the project (for example Mutual Learning and Twinning events), to further integrate changes and strengthen interventions.

2.3.3. Step 3: Co-creation and Development of Strategic KPIs

Throughout the execution of UCC's Evaluation and Impact Assessment methodology, particularly during the first two phases of process consisting of the Formative aspect, the implementing partners constantly refined their Action Plans and Transformational Pathways, which produced ever more **focused Key Performance Indicators** to identify and monitor the progress of their interventions.

This process of refinement was conducted with the assistance and guidance of UCC and the feedback/contributions of the other facilitating partners and EAB.

As already mentioned in section 2.2.2 of this report, and in a more detailed form in Deliverable 4.1, the selection of the KPIs for each HEI followed a **standardized and replicable structure**. This method ensured the identification of appropriate KPIs which were not excessive and which would supplement, rather than dominate, the evaluation and monitoring of the interventions. The KPI selection process ensured that the indicators could be practically monitored, taking into consideration the need around data availability, reliability and ease of collection. Furthermore, the number of indicators was kept purposely low, concentrating on

few, highly impactful, strategic, long-term and institutionally embedded KPIs, rather than a large number of relatively unimportant indicators. For this purpose, whenever possible, UCC and the HEIs tried to stay away from KPIs which were overly concentrated on numerical or quantitative monitoring and instead focused on selecting indicators which showcased meaningful and impactful long-term transformation.

To summarize, UCC's methodology for selecting **Strategic KPIs followed 5 key principles**:

- 1 – SMART KPIs (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-based),
- 2 – Outcome and Impact focused and based on realistic, accessible and reliable data,
- 3 – Strategic in nature as opposed to overly operational,
- 4 – Interconnected and/or cumulative i.e. “will the delivery of one mutually reinforce and support the delivery of another?”,
- 5 – Leading not lagging i.e. “will they bring us closer to the delivery of the desired objectives?”.

FIGURE 7: SMART KPIs DIAGRAM, FOSSIL CONSULTING.

This methodology and the principles behind it were further consolidated thanks to the **feedback provided by EAB**. In both the first and second round of recommendations, as already mentioned in the previous section, the external advisors underlined the importance of **selecting few, highly focused, impactful and strategic indicators**. These recommendations were consistent and in-line with UCC's evaluation during the formative process and further encouraged the refinement of the indicators throughout the project.

Furthermore, the use of certain Acceleration Services, provided by the facilitating partners, gave the HEIs extra tools to finetune their indicators. The clearest example of this came from the Reinforce Human Capital service (Mutual Learning and Twinning events), which allowed the Implementers to constantly sense-check and refine their indicators as they interacted and learned from the other partners.

By the end of July 2025, following the second set of bilateral meetings with the Implementers, the summative self-assessment survey and the second EAB feedback, UCC was able to co-create and provide a **monitoring tool for the Strategic KPIs to each implementing partner** (Annex G). The tool, which responded to the key principles which guided their selection process, was the product of careful communication and co-design with each of the HEIs and contained a detailed description of the indicator, its monitoring parameters and its delivery status. The Strategic KPI monitoring tool was built on Microsoft Excel for ease of use and familiarity with the institution representatives.

Each HEI's list of Strategic KPIs and tool will be examined, in detail and on a case-by-case basis in the results section of this report (Section 3.1) in the case studies.

Toolkit Step 3

1. Throughout the project, utilize the information gathered in the initial steps, baseline data, partner's contributions and ToC Narrative to construct initial version of KPI selection and Action Plan progress monitor (*example of this can be found in Annex G*).
2. Constantly sense-check and test the KPIs to ensure that they match the Five Strategic KPI principles:
 - a. SMART KPIs (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-based)
 - b. Outcome and Impact focused and based on realistic, accessible and reliable data
 - c. Strategic in nature as opposed to overly operational
 - d. Interconnected and/or cumulative i.e. "will the delivery of one mutually reinforce and support the delivery of another?"
 - e. Leading not lagging i.e. "will they bring us closer to the delivery of the desired objectives?"
3. Validate KPIs with EAB.
4. Finalize Strategic KPI tool to visualize and monitor Action Plan and indicators (*examples of this can be found in each Case Study in Chapter 3 of this report*).

2.3.4. Step 4: Summative Evaluation Tool

Following the second set of bilateral meetings between UCC and the Implementers between April and May 2025, the **Summative aspect** of the evaluation was conducted. This aspect of the evaluation was in the form of a comprehensive, end-of-project, self-assessment and structured survey which was conducted throughout June of 2025.

UCC decided to enhance and refine the approach for the Summative approach by employing a self-assessment survey as the anonymized structure of the questionnaire would allow for more truthful and accurate information and assessments to be developed as opposed to direct interviews. The survey was conceived as a tool to complement the summative and formative component of WP4 and was aligned with the ToC process and the selection of Strategic KPIs set out in Deliverable 4.1 and presented to the implementing partners at the beginning of the project's evaluation phase.

The design process and creation of the survey took approximately one month to complete and was built using Microsoft Forms for ease of use and accessibility. The survey was primarily built around being self-reflective and contained both qualitative elements (open questions and text boxes for opinions) and quantitative elements (rating and voting with the use of sliders) to assess level of utilization, appreciation etc. of different elements of CATALISI, particularly the Acceleration Services.

Both Facilitators and Implementers were invited to respond to the survey. For the purposes of conciseness, only one form was completed per organization, and the survey results were kept anonymous. The outputs of the survey were shared with the CATALISI partners and informed the next, and final phases of the evaluation. Furthermore, the data collected contained elements useful to both EY and F6S, respectively in their work surrounding the **Policy Recommendation** and **Exploitation/Dissemination**. Finally, in designing the survey, UCC took careful consideration in aligning it with the ethos of the **ERA Policy Agenda 2022-**

2024 and 2025-2027 (that was in the adoption process by the Council of the EU) and the principles of CATALISI to explore, co-design, implement and evaluate.

The survey was open for the entire month of June 2025, and the topics covered were as follows:

- **Action plan implementation.**
- **Key achievements to date obtained by the facilitating and implementing partners.**
- **Embedding of the action plans within the HEIs.**
- **Self-Reflection on the CATALISI project by the partners.**
- **Main learnings from CATALISI.**
- **Unanticipated opportunities stemming from the projects and their interactions.**
- **WP5 exploitation and dissemination information useful for F6S.**
- **Acceleration Services Utilization, Usefulness, Reproducibility, Recommendations.**

The results of the questionnaire were showcased during the CATALISI monthly meeting of September to the project partners to sense-check the findings and was further illustrated during the final general assembly of CATALISI hosted by AUMC in Amsterdam, in November of 2025. During this event, the results were presented in the final CATALISI conference, as well as discussed in the validation workshop, alongside the Formative evaluation results, in the final coordination meeting the day prior.

As previously mentioned, several sections of the survey were specifically catered to providing information and data to fellow facilitating partners. In particular, EY utilized the findings, especially the self-reflection and recommendation sections, to feed the Policy Recommendations developed in T4.5. F6S was able to leverage the section which concentrated on the dissemination and exploitation of the project, as per WP5. The survey results were also utilized and fed into Deliverables 1.3 and 2.3.

The findings of the survey will be analyzed, in depth, in the results section of this report (Section 3.2).

Toolkit Step 4

1. Build Summative Evaluation Tool which will assess, ex-post, the efficacy and execution of the project and the Partner's interventions.
2. The Summative tool should include, but should not be limited to, these sections to assess key elements of the project:
 - a. Integration of relevant actions and interventions,
 - b. Key achievement by each partner until that point,
 - c. Embedding actions and interventions in the Partner's institution,
 - d. Self-reflection by each Partner on the project's work,
 - e. Main learnings, from the perspective of the partner,
 - f. Unanticipated opportunities stemming from the project,
 - g. Utilization, usefulness and reproducibility of the tools, services and methodologies present in the project.
 - h. Summary recommendations from the Partners.
3. Analyse, produce aggregate results of the survey in internal report and sense-check the findings in a presentation and/or validation workshop.

*Refer to **Annex H and I** for a concrete example of a Summative Self-Evaluation Survey as per the one conducted by UCC in CATALISI and an example of a GDPR-Compliant Model Consent Form for when sharing surveys and interviews.*

2.3.5. Step 5: Develop Monitoring and Evaluation Dashboard

UCC has developed a Dashboard as an additional or supplementary component of the CATALISI Evaluation and Impact Assessment Toolkit, complementing the Theory of Change methodology, formative evaluation techniques, and summative assessment instruments. Its aim is providing a centralised, accessible, and visually compelling presentation of KPI data and its development was set out in Deliverable 4.1 in relation to the Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan. The CATALISI KPI Dashboard which presents the same KPI data in a more accessible and real time format than as presented statically in the Case Study Section of Section 3 below, will represent a practical application of the project's commitment to further embedding evaluation culture within participating HEIs. The Dashboard is a bespoke digital monitoring and visualisation tool developed to support the real-time tracking and reporting of Strategic Key Performance Indicators selected by any HEI using the tool. The Dashboard will serve as a central platform for consolidating evaluation data, enabling stakeholders to monitor institutional progress post project, identify trends, and communicate outcomes effectively to internal and external stakeholders. The CATALISI KPI Dashboard represents also an important impact for UCC and a Key Exploitable Result (KER).

FIGURE 8: HOMEPAGE OF UCC'S CATALISI KPI MONITORING DASHBOARD AS PER THE PRE-ALPHA VERSION.

FIGURE 9: ANALYTICS SECTION OF THE CATALISI KPI MONITORING DASHBOARD AS PER THE PRE-ALPHA VERSION.

Toolkit Step 5

1. Build upon the work conducted throughout the project and develop a monitoring tool to identify, co-design, co-create and monitor the indicators selected.
2. The tool should be easy to use, accessible, co-created by the Partners and integrated in the Evaluation process.
3. The tool should include all the principles regarding KPI selection of Step 3.
4. The tool should complement, not dominate, the Evaluation process.

2.3.6. Ex-Post Monitoring and Toolkit Conclusions

As it will become evident in the Seven Case Studies section of Chapter 3 of this report, most interventions by the implementing partners were designed to produce outcomes and impacts within the time confines of the CATALISI project. That said, UCC's methodology and Toolkit, as described and prescribed so far in the preceding steps, constitutes a standardized and reproducible process which can be replicated by the CATALISI partners, as well as any higher education institution wishing to replicate this methodology in their own context specific environment.

The HEIs were provided with KPI monitoring tools, in the form of Excel sheets, templates, discussion frameworks and tools which will be easily updated and expanded with further interventions and data, and which are illustrated in the Annex of this report. This, alongside the process templates produced throughout the project and illustrated in the Toolkit steps, will allow the implementing partners to replicate the same actions and activities which aided in their co-design and co-creation of their respective Action Plans and Transformational Pathways.

The Strategic KPI Tool, present in each HEI's case study, and the Monitoring Dashboard presented in the preceding section, represent an important result, but by no means the final step in the toolkit hitherto illustrated. More comprehensively, the entire process, consisting of the steps, modalities, templates, guides and frameworks, condensed in the Toolkit presented in this report, constitute a standardized and replicable framework for the partners for follow-up, ex-post monitoring of their ongoing interventions, or the development of new ones.

In particular, the introductory presentation to the ToC approach conducted in Step 1 (M17), and the follow-up ToC workshop (M21), provided the implementers with comprehensive training in the Theory of Change methodology, giving them the necessary theoretical underpinning and understanding to replicate this Toolkit in the future. This, alongside the material provided in the Annex of this report (in particular **Annex D** and the Logic Model Template in **Annex L**) will allow the CATALISI partners to start undertaking this same methodology and use the Toolkit to launch new R&I interventions on institutional change or continue the monitoring of ongoing ones.

3. RESULTS

The Monitoring and Evaluation results (of the formative and summative elements of the evaluative approach) are presented in the form of 7 comparable case studies and the results of a summative assessment. Each case study is centred on one of the Implementing Partners. Subsequently, we will present the results of the summative component. The formative analysis of the data, which comprises the bulk of the qualitative results, are mostly outlined in the case studies, while the summative analysis, primarily deriving from the survey, represents the majority of the mixed methods data.

The Case Studies are the culmination of the Formative Evaluation while the self-assessment survey constitutes the culmination of the Summative component of the Evaluations conducted ex-post in the project. Although each Case Study contains institutional-specific summaries, observations and considerations, these will be unified with the summative evaluation findings of the survey for a complete and holistic overview of the project in the final, conclusion chapter of this report.

3.1. CASE STUDIES (7)

Below are the case studies of each of the seven HEIs in the CATALISI project. Each case study has a quick overview of the institution, followed by an in-depth view of their Theory of Change narrative, overview of their transformational pathways, results stemming from the project (in terms of outputs, outcomes and impacts) and a final summary of their case study. The case studies should be viewed as the culmination of the formative evaluation process illustrated in the previous section of this report. That said, inputs and further information, which led to the writing of these case studies, also originated from other sources, as described in Sections 2.1 and 2.3 of this report. The case studies will be followed by Section 3.2, with an in-depth look at the results stemming from the Summative component of the evaluation.

3.1.1. Case Study 1: KTU

Overview

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) in Lithuania aims to be a leading science and innovation university blending education with research. KTU is a technical university founded in 1920, it has moved from 13 to 9 faculties in a reform process in 2014 to address efficiency. It has a comprehensive orientation comprising social science and humanities mixed with technology. The university aims to offer top-quality research-based studies, create and share knowledge for sustainable development, and provide a creative environment that inspires leaders and talent. One of their objectives is to enhance research reputation at both regional and European levels. This includes ensuring that their R&I systems efficiently share research outcomes with both academic audiences and the broader public. KTU's vision is to be an interdisciplinary university, competitive at the international level, developing and transferring new knowledge and innovations.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, KTU highlighted the following context that inform the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. Lithuania's system is performance based. It involves five-year university evaluations and impact case studies that are linked to performance-based funding. The idea is to cultivate impact-oriented teaching and research across the higher education landscape. While many elements of this system are positive, the approach can also reduce the freedom of academics to pursue curiosity-driven or fundamental research, as they may feel pressured to align their work with defined short term performance indicators, whereas potentially groundbreaking, research takes many years to yield significant results. The effect is also placing an overemphasis on publication counts rather than the quality or scientific excellence of the research. For former technical institutions like KTU, they have fewer resources to reorient around impact, while facing rising expectations. Systemic issues they highlighted include:

- Low levels of international mobility, particularly amongst early career researchers.
- Unequal capacities of first stage researchers in academic writing leading to a low number of publications (*Human Capital*)
- Underdevelopment of interdisciplinary approaches in the publications and project proposals at the university.
- No institutional strategy for fostering first time international *mobility*.
- Undeveloped coordination of international mobility with strategic research and study fields.
- Relative lack of awareness regarding the public engagement (which is central to achieving societal impact) and the principles of citizen science (*Public Engagement*).
- Underdeveloped knowledge of researchers to engage in citizen science research.
- Absence of actor networks including quadruple helix actors for the development of citizen science projects and impact-oriented research.

Secondly, KTU initially articulated the following issues they wished to address including the need to support and encourage talent circulation and mobility, with a specific focus on early career researchers. Currently KTU has an obligatory Erasmus exchange for staff, this must occur twice every 5 years and is compulsory for staff to achieve higher pay. This was very effective in promoting motivation for mobility. In January 2025 there were twice as many requests for mobility compared to the previous year, however, half were rejected. This was caused by competitiveness for Erasmus mobility funding. Their short-term goal was to create a survey to evaluate the best response to this situation. The long-term goal is to create guidelines to promote effective mobility.

The need to strengthen services for academic writing in KTU: KTU has established a "writing clinic" which aims at training students to write scientific papers, especially in English. However, its services are currently quite narrowly focussed on doctoral students, and the services are not widely used. The short-term goal was to conduct a survey of writing clinic potential users through contacts established with their doctoral school and with other bodies within university. The medium-term goal, based on the data produced by the survey, is designing a service expansion. The long-term objective is expanding the KTU Writing Clinic to a wider audience, beyond the current doctoral users.

The need to deepen the institutions Citizen Science activities was articulated as a specific priority. Their assumption is that through identifying potential audiences and providing training to KTU researchers and civil society on citizen science, this will raise awareness of the concept. This involves creating a roadmap on how to effectively engage the public in research, particularly the inclusion of external stakeholders in co-solving societal problems.

In the short-term, KTU's goal is to enact and implement a Citizen Science Hub. The long-term goal is to develop a HEI which implements social change through research and does this through cooperation with society to a high standard.

Transformation Pathways

At the beginning of the initiative, KTU performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

KTU focussed on 2 domains and 3 intervention areas:

- Research careers and talent support:
 - Supporting talent circulation and mobility
 - Strengthening of human capital
- Research modus operandi:
 - Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where UCC supported KTU to adopt the recommendations of the External Acceleration Board (EAB). KTU's first action plan was fragmented in nature and contained 15 loosely connected KPIs across concepts relating to mobility, a writing clinic and public engagement, among other areas. The KPIs were operational and not strategic in nature and primarily connected to events and tasks that were somewhat removed from change and impact. The EAB commented on goals being too broad and needing more specific actions. There was a need for stronger links to national and European policies, clearer impact metrics, and more engagement with external stakeholders. Overall, the plan was solid but would benefit from more detailed long-term strategies and improved stakeholder involvement. Subsequently, KTU improved its strategic focus by updating the domains and intervention areas to better align with institutional priorities and stakeholder needs. In particular, the updated plan refocused only on two main domains (Research careers and talent support, and Research Modus Operandi, abandoning an original inclusion of the domain of Sustainable research and education), and a focus on three core intervention areas.

Transformation Focus		
Talent Mobility	Human Capital	Public Engagement
Identify obstacles to international mobility via surveys and interviews. Develop guidelines on fostering first time international mobility.	Understand need regarding academic writing via surveys and interviews. Action plan for strengthening of university-based services for academic writing.	Applying a living lab methodology for creating dialogue with quadruple helix stakeholders on enabling and strengthening a citizen science hub. Prepare interactive trainings and lectures on citizen science. Develop a roadmap on how to effectively engage public in research. Communicate the added value of public engagement.

TABLE 6: KTU TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Results (Outputs and Outcomes)

KTU established a CATALISI Team responsible for one set of actions and KPIs within their Action Plan. There were three major areas of implementation (goals) - two for human capital and one for public engagement. They implemented a living lab methodology for co-creating solutions for identified challenges. The progress KTU made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
KTU 1	With the goal of strengthening university-wide services to support increased competencies of academic staff to publish their research in quality journals and books, KTU will develop a writing clinic action plan by October 2025 and operationalise the writing clinic by December 2025.	Writing Clinic and Action Plan		Y	Writing Clinic is up and running and plan is in place. Survey stakeholders to evaluate and enhance further post-project
KTU 2	To support talent circulation and mobility, while enhancing the reputation of KTU internationally, KTU will prepare and embed informed strategic guidelines to foster first-time staff mobility at KTU by December 2025.	Strategic Guidelines First-Time mobility.		Y	Guidelines developed based on co-creative work with Academic Mobility Office, International Coordinator, Academic staff and relevant committee.
KTU 3	To embed Citizen Science at KTU and to actively promote public engagement and outreach with the general public for the betterment of research and society, KTU will systematically raise awareness of the Citizen Science Hub at KTU in 2023-24 and develop a road map for embedding Citizen Science by December 2025. This will include the development of best practices on how to effectively engage public stakeholders in KTU research.	Citizen Science Road Map		Y	Trainings and Public Lectures completed in 2024, Roadmap for CS and best practices developed in 2025, Currently being finalised.

FIGURE 10: KTU STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

KTU demonstrated a strong commitment to the CATALISI initiative and was responsive in implementing the changes suggested by both UCC and the EAB in their Action Plans and Transformational Pathways. After an initial revision the institution re-focused their activities on specific Actions and related KPIs. The final, revised set of indicators (and focus) has resulted in a higher level of implementation and more embedded and strategic nature of the actions being pursued by the institution.

KTU leveraged specific Acceleration Services, such as the Living Lab, while engaging with others as relevant to their action plans. The institution achieved scientific and social impact thanks to their revised guidelines on career mobility, improved writing clinic, and citizen science road map. The Writing Clinic, Strategic Guideline for First-Time Mobility and the Citizen Science Roadmap all ensure a clear and straightforward path for long-term impact of the activities and objectives set out throughout the CATALISI project.

Summary

KTU underwent a positive transformational journey through taking on board the feedback of UCC's formative evaluation approach and that of the EAB, and in addition ENOLL and EY. KTU was also open to change and adaptive throughout the project and learned from other partners, including both facilitators and implementers. Upon finishing the project KTU had three clear, well defined strategic KPIs, clearly owned, aligned with the strategy of the University, and set out until 2028.

KTU has developed a comprehensive set of sustainability measures to support its transformational pathway beyond the project's formal end. These measures are closely aligned with the post-project activities and reflect best practices and lessons learned throughout the project. By embedding these recommendations into its long-term strategy, KTU aims to secure the continuity and resilience of institutional change, ensuring that the benefits realized during CATALISI will endure and evolve.

- The transformational actions progressed are aligned with KTU's strategic goal of becoming a research-intensive university with a focus on fundamental knowledge and a strong academic identity.
- KTU made significant progress by reducing and re-focusing KPIs and narrowing down its focus to three priority areas, improving feasibility and potential for impact.

- A next step is embedding and sustaining the CATALISI activities in the institution for long-term impact.
 - Retaining a Living Lab as a permanent approach within KTU to enable institutional innovation, will assist with ongoing change processes.
 - KTU is well positioned to consolidate their focus on research-societal engagement through institutionalising and embedding a framework and commitments to HEI '3rd Mission' within their strategic plans.
 - The preparation of Research Council of Lithuania Impact Case Studies is a potential lever for driving change, especially on impact-oriented or engaged teaching and research examples to enable performance based national funding.
 - In addition, institutionalising a Living Lab as a long-term structure can mobilise a quadruple helix approach together with citizens, researchers, local authorities, and industry to co-create research & innovation.
 - Risk mitigation strategies for first-time talent mobility need strengthening particularly if participation rates remain low. Institutional incentives to encourage academic mobility amongst Early Career Researchers could be considered.

In summary KTU demonstrated a high level of efficacy with a focus on long-term impact and strategic change within KTU for the future. A specific and impactful legacy from the CATALISI initiative is the development of KTU's first ever set of strategic guidelines to support staff mobility. Embedding this practice at the University will result in Economic, Social and Scientific impacts, post-project. Similarly, the establishment of the academic writing clinic and related plan, will accelerate formal scientific impact emanating from KTU, post-project.

3.1.2. Case Study 2: UJI

Overview

Universitat Jaume I (UJI), is located in Castellón de la Plana, Spain, is a public university established in 1991. It has around 12,000 students and is noted for its commitment to quality education and particularly for its commitment to institutional change. In recent years, this agenda began with the ETHNA project focused on research ethics, and has since expanded through CATALISI to include research assessment, open science and ethical governance systems to promote good practices in responsible research and innovation (RRI) within higher education institutions, UJI seeks to develop interventions aligned with the National Open Science Strategy (ENCA). This strategy sets a series of measures and goals such as the promotion and strengthening of transparency, quality and reproducibility of research results. UJI aims to ease researchers' access to information by adopting a multidimensional approach to open science, including public repositories and open access peer-reviewed journals. Additionally, UJI is working on developing criteria that combine qualitative and quantitative methods for research assessment. Finally, UJI is working to improve its research ethics committee procedures and protocols.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, UJI highlighted the following context that informs the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. They described a relative underfunding of research in Spain, and a high level of bureaucracy, which create a challenging environment for sustaining research. For example, the amounts granted to individual research projects are often small and frequently do not cover salaries for essential staff like students or post-doctoral researchers, who must seek funding elsewhere. This amongst other factors also makes it difficult to attract and retain international talent and has a "brain drain" effect of talented scientists who emigrate for better opportunities.

Researchers in public universities often face very high teaching loads compared to other countries, which diminishes the time and effort available for research activities. The research evaluation system has been criticized for relying heavily on publishing over other valuable outputs like patents or societal impact. However, recent reforms such as CoARA are attempting to address this by considering a broader range of research outputs. The regulatory framework for research integrity is fragmented and lacks systematic, mandatory guidelines, however there is much work underway to address this. The system is also quiet centralised Universities often have limited autonomy and lack substantial representation from outside society in their governing bodies.

CATALISI came along at a time of change for UJI, A new Vice Rector Research regarded the 'Open' agenda as central to the offices work programme. For example, UJI has a robust program in place for public engagement, complete with a dedicated office and Vice Rector. Therefore, the Institutional Support to promote public engagement is in place. However, what was challenging in a CATALISI context for UJI was the practical engagement of external stakeholders in the specific transformations that UJI were aiming to achieve. In many ways research ethics and reform of research assessment are primarily inward-looking processes, and, in such context, it proved challenging to mobilise the QH stakeholders around these areas. In addition, many disciplines are often one-step removed and more insular and unfamiliar with engaging societal partners active participation in research. CoARA in terms of its implications for changes in how research is performed will meet some initial resistance once this is understood as it will affect how research is performed. Previously with a sole focus on Journals and rankings of journals in terms of prestige - had a quantitative logic. Now the logic is moving to a more qualitative understanding of research in terms of its impact, requiring greater levels of public engagement. This is radical and likely to have push back as entrenched views and the status quo are challenged. Re-imagining research is now very much in vogue, but for UJI this can also threaten and empower more traditional and conservative thinking.

UJI also highlighted that their systems for ethical approval need review. Form a position of no control at all in Spain, they are now moving to a system of high control nationally and locally, and this effects the area of ethics particularly, whereas previously there was trust, now that cannot be assumed, especially as universities in Europe become more research intensive. The quality of research inevitably is underpinned by ethics, and strong ethical systems. The fact that UJI is a CoARA signatory allows it to leverage this for change, as there are reputational consequences to not delivering on what they have signed up to. UJI specifically highlighted these points:

- The need for the development of new research assessment criteria, with a focus on qualitative measures, and the creation of clear, straightforward criteria for identifying, managing, and evaluating gender mainstreaming in research.
- The risk of increasing bureaucratic tasks for researchers.

Secondly, UJI initially articulated the following issues they wished to address in response to the context articulated above.

- Creation of a university action plan approved by the university's governing bodies on research evaluation. Transform or adapt the internal evaluation system of UJI to seek a balance between qualitative and quantitative criteria in scientific assessment; Redefining UJI evaluation "scale". UJI is adjusting research assessment in the institution: grants are now being given with a greater emphasis on qualitative assessment and based less, as it was in the past, on impact assessment. This change has occurred thanks to both CATALISI (and the work conducted by the UJI team), as well as to a general cultural and mentality change which the team has noted within their institution.
- Develop an OA "Thermometer" (inspired by experiences from other universities). Aimed at learning about similar experiences in other institutions (including from other CATALISI members). It provides the ability to monitor the percentage of open access research carried out at UJI. Survey of Research Assessment and Open Science. Conducted a survey on academic staff on their engagement with open access.
- Reviewing (and transforming) the functioning of UJI's ethic committees for research. This is a redefinition of the structure of the tools that guide research ethics within the institution.

Transformation Pathways

At the beginning of the initiative, UJI performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

UJI focused on 2 main domains and 3 intervention areas:

- Research careers and talent support:
 - Recognition of qualifications and research careers.
 - Reform of research assessment.
- Research modus operandi:
 - Mainstreaming of open science and digitisation of research.

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where UCC supported UJI to adopt the recommendations of the External Acceleration Board (EAB). UJI's first action plan was slightly vague and difficult to monitor. It had eight largely operational KPIs identified, requiring the development of a more strategic approach. The EAB commented on goals being too broad and needing more specific actions. The reviewers noted mechanisms for external stakeholder involvement and resource allocation need clearer definition. They noted the need to set measurable KPIs and practical follow-up activities to enhance the plan's impact and sustainability. Subsequently, UJI, with support from UCC, improved its strategic focus by updating the domains and intervention areas to better align with institutional strategic priorities.

Transformation Focus		
Research Assessment	Open Science	Ethics
Review and update evaluation policies in line with COARA. Achieve a university action plan, conducting targeted surveys, and redefining the evaluation scale,	Enact Open Science principles and policies. Develop strong indicators, launching the OA thermometer, and recognizing best practices.	Modernize and strengthen the role of UJI's research ethics committees,

<p>Ensure policies are evidence-based and aligned with national reforms.</p> <p>Establish small, specialized working groups focused on the intervention areas.</p> <p>Ensure close collaboration between the university's top management, the academic community, and the members of the CATALISI project.</p> <p>Enable deliberation processes with key stakeholder groups (focus group) and consultation with the academic community (survey) on topics.</p> <p>Embed within university's governance bodies focused on open science and research evaluation reform.</p>	<p>Create a culture that values transparency, accessibility, and innovation in research.</p> <p>Achieve an approach to open science that is measurable, visible, and sustainable.</p> <p>Position the institution as a leader in open research practices at both the national and European levels.</p>	<p>Ensure that ethical review processes are both efficient and robust.</p> <p>Reviewing committee operations, producing clear communication materials, and offering targeted training.</p> <p>Foster a culture of integrity and ethical awareness across the research community.</p> <p>Ensure that ethical standards remain central to all research activities at the university.</p>
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TABLE 7: UJI TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Results (Outputs and Outcomes)

UJI established a CATALISI Team responsible for delivering the actions and KPIs within their Action Plan. There were three major areas of implementation supported by a Living Lab methodology for co-creating solutions to identified challenges. Initially, objectives were ill-defined and overly ambitious, requiring greater delineation. A challenge was to set realistic, strategic and measurable KPIs and practical follow-up activities. However, while UJI's objectives were ambitious, they demonstrated a high level of adaptability and responsiveness to the EAB and UCC's analytic feedback, making real time continuous improvements. As they revised and refined their set of actions and indicators, they achieved a pioneering set of goals for the university as well as a pragmatic and focused approach to institutional change. The progress UJI made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
UJI 1	Open Access & Reform of Research Assessment Plans in place at UJI to 2027 and being systematically implemented.	Open Access & Research Assessment Plans		Y	OA and Research Assessment plans in place, governance in place. Implementation phase commenced. Clear owner. Linked to National Orgs and Initiatives
UJI 2	Open Access Thermometer (State of the Art for UJI) completed in 2024. Results to be analysed in 2025 and outcomes to further inform the Open Access Plan to 2027 to maximise impact.	Open Access Thermometer		Y	Results sighted, Feedback via OA Plan for 2026, 2027.
UJI 3	Advancement of UJI's ethical research processes and protocols including a thorough review of research ethics procedures, the development (and implementation) of a new code of code practice in research and doctoral training as well as the development of additional smart research ethics resources in 2025, to positively impact the research ethics agenda at UJI.	Review of Ethical Research processes and new code of practice		Y	Review completed, New code of practice in research and doctoral training.

FIGURE 11: UJI STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

Their primary activities (Open Access & Research Assessment Plans, Open Access Thermometer, CoARA Action Plan and the Review of Ethical Research Processes, in combination with the New Code of Practice) fully encapsulate UJI's long-term goals by combining an ambitious set of indicators to monitor future institutional change, while at the same time not losing sight of the necessity to render the actions and indicators achievable and measurable. All three-intervention area (research assessment, Open Science, and research ethics/recognition of qualifications) are aligned with national and European frameworks.

They now have formal institutional frameworks that extend beyond the end of CATALISI. Of note are the CoARA-UJI Action Plan (2024–2027) and the Open Science (ENCA-UJI) Action Plan. These ensure effective institutionalising, clear milestones, governance, an implementation processes. The earlier planned public engagement actions were a challenge due to an emerging and relatively underdeveloped societal engagement agenda and culture at UJI.

Overall, UJI displayed a high level of engagement and alignment with the CATALISI model, particularly engaging with the Living Lab, Twinning and Transformational Pathway; however, engaging with other acceleration services where relevant and timely. They made excellent links with colleagues in AUMC and UCC to advance joint work on Research Culture Ethics and Integrity actions.

Summary

UJI underwent a positive and focused transformational journey as part of the CATALISI initiative. The team did this by being adaptive, willing to learn and open to change as well as bringing a 'follow-through' focus to their activity. UJI integrated the use of acceleration services where appropriate and collaborated well with the other partners as borne out by their partnership with AUMC and UCC on research culture.

In 2023-24 UJI's first action plan was slightly vague and difficult to monitor. It had 8, largely operational KPIs identified. By working with UCC, taking on board the EAB's feedback, fully participating in project events and utilisation of the Mutual Learning Exercise and Twinning acceleration services in particular, UJI presented a far more focused set of KPIs in 2025. These KPIs were clear, meaningful in the UJI context, were embedded strategically in the University governance structures and are clearly owned. These will undoubtedly help the university continue their focus on open science and reform of research assessment into the future.

To ensure that the achievements of the transformational pathway extend beyond the project's lifetime, UJI has committed to several sustainability measures. UJI has secured sustainability beyond CATALISI by embedding change into two multi-year institutional action plans that run through 2027: specifically, the CoARA-UJI Action Plan on research assessment reform, and also the Open Science (ENCA-UJI) Action Plan.

- The transformational actions progressed are aligned with UJI's strategic goals as a teaching and research-intensive university – especially its objective of establishing a culture of responsible research.
- UJI made significant progress through a re-focusing of KPIs and focus on three priority areas, which improved feasibility and potential for impact.
- All three areas (research assessment, Open Science, and research ethics/recognition of qualifications) are strategic and mutually reinforcing.
- UJI established formal institutional frameworks, clear milestones, governance, and implementation processes. These local policy anchors are resilient and binding institutional commitments.
- In the future a public engagement focus for UJI could be initiated through a structured 'public engagement strategy' process and framework, building on learning from European best practice. Mapping the local stakeholder ecosystem and involving them in this could be a positive first step.

In summary, UJI achieved clear scientific and social impact as noted in the examples of advancing Open Science, CoARA implementation and a review of their ethical research framework. The evidence demonstrates that UJI demonstrated a high level of efficacy as regards the CATALISI model with a focus on long-term impact and strategic change within

UJI for the future. The evidence shows that the institution is well positioned to continue its long-term and impactful strategic transformation.

For UJI the evaluation and impact assessment revealed the key legacy impact of the CATALISI project - the Open Access and Reform of Research Assessment plans are now in place and being actively delivered at a university-wide level. Beyond that, the plans are robust, data informed and practical and bespoke to UJI. Scientific and Social Impact was therefore accelerated and delivered during the CATALISI project. Furthermore, UJI has been successful in cleverly leveraging and scaling this impact through active participation and leadership at national and international fora on Open Science and the reform of Research Assessment.

3.1.3. Case Study 3: LUISS

Overview

LUISS University (Luiss Libera Università Internazionale degli Studi Sociali Guido Carli), located in Rome, Italy, is a prestigious independent university founded in 1974. It offers a wide range of undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs through its six departments: Accounting and Corporate Finance; AI, Data and Decision Sciences; Business and Management; Economics and Financial Markets; Law; Political Science. LUISS is well-known for its innovative educational approach, combining academic rigor with practical relevance. LUISS excels in social sciences research, particularly in economics, history, political science, sociology, law, and management. The university is involved in numerous high-quality research projects and collaborations, contributing significantly to these fields. The university's research strategy focuses on interdisciplinary themes that impact strategy, teaching, and societal action. It has a leading focus on its Third Mission and set of activities through which it interacts directly with civil society and business to promote the economic, social and cultural growth. It is committed to engaging academic and research outputs as a tool for generating an impact on society.

Guided by this vision to become an international laboratory where knowledge and societal and business innovation converge, Luiss promotes interdisciplinary research and integrates emerging technologies to create positive, measurable social impact. Internationalization is a cornerstone of this strategy. LUISS Guido Carli University is part of a new transformation, that aims to introduce structural changes in policies, processes, and funding to especially enhance research excellence and advance Open Science. Through global partnerships and participation in major research networks, LUISS supports faculty and researchers in developing high-impact, cross-border projects. LUISS University aims to advance its Open Science agenda by raising awareness among faculty, staff, and governance, and by improving the overall quality and visibility of Open Access publications. This effort reflects broader cultural shift towards transparency, collaboration, and shared knowledge as pillars of research excellence. At the same time, the University is committed to attracting top talents through improved policies and incentive schemes, supporting participation in international programmes such as MSCA and ERC.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, LUISS highlighted the following context that informs the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. An important contextual factor for LUISS is that the university operates in a national system that is relatively underfunded. Italy's research

spending is significantly lower than the European average (around 1% of GDP compared to the EU average of over 2%). In Italy, this has resulted in a lack of resources for research projects, research infrastructure challenges, and issues in attracting researchers from abroad. Indeed, LUISS highlighted talent circulation and mobility as an opportunity for, which if strengthened, can enhance research quality and international competitiveness, addressing brain drain issues. Similarly, they discussed their goal of improving the responsiveness of research, which they interpret as laying the groundwork for a culture of openness and collaboration, and particularly deepening and extending their 3rd Mission commitments to bring research into partnership with business and society. A particular goal is to position LUISS as a leader in the adoption of open research practices, which will contribute they believe to enhancing its competitiveness and societal impact.

They highlighted the need to specifically:

- Strengthen participation in talent circulation and mobility initiatives as part of a desire to promote an open, dynamic, and competitive academic environment, positioning LUISS competitively at the European level.
- Enhance institutional commitment to Open Science as both a policy priority and a practical approach to enhance the quality, efficiency, and responsiveness of research. The university's strategy aims to foster a culture of openness, transparency, and collaboration across all levels—faculty, administrative staff, and governance—by embedding OS principles into daily research practices and institutional policies.
- Extend awareness internally and externally of its Third Mission focus, promoting active dialogue and collaboration between academia and society, and ensuring that research outcomes contribute to addressing real-world challenges.

Secondly, LUISS initially articulated the following issues they wished to address in response to the context articulated above.

- Focus on stimulating a positive research culture to promote excellence in research, especially supporting researcher development through supporting applications to Maria Skłodowska-Curie Action (MSCA) and European Research Council (ERC) funding.
- Advance a positive research culture also via Open Science (OS) through increasing awareness between staff, governance and researchers in LUISS.
- Build awareness internally and externally of its Third-Mission through a Promotion Campaign.

Transformation Pathways

At the beginning of the initiative, LUISS performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

LuiSS focussed on 2 main domains and 3 intervention areas:

- Research careers and talent support:
 - Supporting talent circulation and mobility.
 - Research modus operandi:
- Mainstreaming of open science and digitalisation of research.

- Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where UCC supported LUISS to adopt the recommendations of the External Acceleration Board (EAB). LUISS first action plan was overly ambitious and included 27 KPIs which were operational in nature with a focus on events and information sharing.

LUISS subsequently refocused around formative input from UCC and EAB feedback in relation to their activity and performance indicators. Subsequently, LUISS transformation pathway was much more clearly defined and strategically aligned, with clear objectives, measurable outputs, and strong operational commitment.

Transformation Focus		
Research Excellence	Open Science	3 rd Mission (Public Engagement)
<p>Communication of funding opportunities through monthly communications.</p> <p>Organisation of seminars with a focus on MSCA and ERC opportunities.</p> <p>Sponsoring of external seminars (training opportunities) through communications.</p> <p>Support to faculty for ERC and MSCA applications.</p> <p>Improve Luiss incentive policies to attract ERC and MSCA talents.</p>	<p>EU guidelines on Open Science.</p> <p>Update of Luiss webpage with resources for Open Access and Open Science.</p> <p>Hold trainings on tools to publish in Open Science for European projects.</p> <p>Provision of incentives to publish in Open Access, connected to internal research evaluation criteria.</p>	<p>This area of intervention can be best described as a full-on "Third Mission Promotion Campaign" which is being pursued by LUISS.</p> <p>Launch of questionnaires on the awareness on Third Mission in general.</p> <p>Presentation of the Third Mission Office.</p> <p>Creation of multimedia contents.</p> <p>Restyling of the University website to enhance the Third Mission and public engagement.</p> <p>Participation to multiple courses on Third Mission and to the activities of the networks and national consortia.</p> <p>Research newsletter to include Third Mission</p> <p>Organise an event to promote LUISS research to the wider public (LUISS Research Day).</p> <p>Strengthen LUISS's role in national and international debates on the Third Mission by participating in major networks and consortia</p>

TABLE 8: LUISS TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Results (Outputs and Outcomes)

LUISS' presented a broad and ambitious set of objectives at the beginning of the CATALISI project. Their Transformational Pathway and Action Plan was refined through UCC's bilateral meetings and the EAB's assessments. The LUISS CATALISI team engaged in a high level of responsiveness and integration of the adjustments and recommendations made by UCC and the EAB. The final set of actions and indicators demonstrate a stronger and more focused approach when it comes to the feasibility of the transformation, while not having lost the initial determination and enthusiasm which guided the institution at the beginning. Many activities were combined and integrated and rendered more coherent leading to a more streamlined set of activities and indicators. The progress LUISS made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
LUI 1	In support of talent circulation and mobility and the sustainability of research at Luiss and in line with strategic ambition of Luiss research, Luiss will systematically raise awareness around Marie Curie and ERC research awards in 2023 and 2024 and embed this focus on research excellence in the Research and Third Mission Office by December 2025.	Research Excellence Awareness		Y	Monthly communications, internal seminars delivered. External expertise available to support Research excellence applications. Continued focus in place.
LUI 2	With the aim of attracting research and innovation talent to Luiss conduct a complete review including assessment of current policies in place, assessment of needs and resources available to attract Marie Curie and ERC-level talents to Luiss in 2024. Draft, Approve and implement at least one new policy to support this strategic ambition in 2025.	Policy to attract Research Excellence Talent		Y	Comprehensive review completed. New policy in place to support the attraction of research talent.
LUI 3	With the aim of increasing internal and external awareness of Third Mission activities at Luiss, systematically implement initiatives at Luiss in 2023 and 2024, significantly and strategically adding to the Third Mission Resources. These include a start of the art survey on activities, awareness raising presentations to staff, communications on Third Mission, a re-constructed website including the third mission pillar, embedding Luiss in National Networks, as well as launching an event to promote Luiss to the wider public.	Third Mission Strategic Resources		Y	Survey completed, resources available, participation in national networks. TM more embedded in ongoing communications and outreach activities.

FIGURE 12: LUISS STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

Several actions have already produced noticeable results, such as the promotion of more MSCA and ERA applications. LUISS displayed an active engagement with the project's Acceleration Services, with particular focus on the Transformational Pathway, Capacity Building and Outreach, and Living Lab, showing a strong alignment with the CATALISI model and methodology. Furthermore, LUISS demonstrated clear economic, social and scientific impact thanks to, respectively: a revised policy on research excellence, third mission campaign and increased applications to prestigious academic grants. The Research Excellence Awareness renewed Policy to Attract Research Excellence Talent and the Third Mission Strategic Resource, all present promising potential for future institutional change, and the HEI's pursuit of a deep cultural change in the institution, considering the challenging situation in the surrounding academic ecosystem. This is extremely commendable.

Summary

Luiss underwent a positive and important transformational journey as part of the CATALISI project. The University began the project with very ambitious plans as set out in the 27 KPIs identified as part of their Action Planning process in 2023-24, which were subsequently refined around more strategic approach. Luiss was open to learning and took on board formative input from UCC in relation to their activity and performance indicators. Luiss participated in all project activities and benefited from the third mission experience of the partners. Upon leaving the project, LUISS has co-created three strategic KPIs which are university-wide, embedded strategically, and will bring them closer to the change they want to continue to affect.

- LUISS had a change of PI in 2024 and should be commended for retaining momentum and for progress made in 2025 in particular.
- LUISS made significant progress, displayed responsiveness throughout the evaluation process by integrating feedback, a refining of KPIs and focus on three priority areas, which improved feasibility and potential for impact.
- The transformation pathway defined by LUISS is clearly defined and strategically aligned, with clear short-, medium-, and long-term objectives, measurable outputs, and embedded incentives that show a strong operational commitment.
- However, some work is needed to ensure the range of outputs mobilised have the desired effect in achieving the outcomes intended and realise longer institutional change and impact.

- Where outputs might be consolidated towards legacy outcomes and impact is through LUISS's post-project sustainability plan. Also, through clarification of long-term funding, ownership, and continued integration and alignment with LUISS's broader institutional strategy.
- LUISS is particularly poised to further develop its Third Mission to incorporate a research 'co-production' paradigm and forms of research engagement that advance research *with* society rather than 'on' or 'for' society, in effect increasing participatory modalities. The LabGov initiative - the *Laboratory for the Governance of the City as a Commons* (Foster and Iaione 2022) - housed in LUISS and a Living Lab approach, could support deepening an internal understanding of *engaged* research and innovation approaches.
- A key impact for Luiss from the CATALISI project is the enhanced third mission activity that was accelerated during the project and the related legacy resources that were put in place, which positions Luiss well for the future. Ultimately, this is helping and will help into the future, the successful delivery of social impact. The work has fostered closer connectivity and collaboration of the University with society, which was a fundamental aim.

LUISS is committed to embedding the initiatives begun under CATALISI into its long-term strategic and operational structures. Actions related to research excellence, talent attraction, Open Science, and the Third Mission are structured to endure through their integration into internal policies, monitoring mechanisms, and support measures. In particular the Research and Third Mission Office are well positioned to support the institutionalisation of transformation practices over time. In summary given this progress and the responsive changes made by the LUISS team through their careful and thoughtful integration of the guidance by the EAB and UCC's recommendations, the institution is well positioned to achieve long-term and impactful institutional change in the foreseeable future.

3.1.4. Case Study 4: UG

Overview

University of Gdańsk is a leading Polish institution with campuses in Gdańsk, Sopot, and Gdynia. It offers a wide range of academic programs and excels in fields like marine science, quantum physics, and biotechnology. As a founding member of the SEA-EU alliance, it drives international research, especially in oceanography. The university is globally recognized through rankings like QS and Times Higher Education and leads major projects such as the Cancer Vaccine Science and Quantum Technologies centres. UG also supports regional innovation and sustainable development through strong industry partnerships.

The University of Gdansk aims to become a prominent institution that enables individuals to realize their potential and achievements, especially through collaboration with business in the context of a research-oriented university. UG is exploring the concept of catalysing transformative changes through stakeholder engagement. It recognizes the importance of collaboration, innovation, and shared responsibility in driving positive societal and environmental impact. The university seeks to promote public engagement through outreach and education activities, mobilizing communities to participate in solving social problems.

Additionally, UG also aspires to achieve sustainability on campus, minimizing environmental impact while promoting social and economic sustainability.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, UG highlighted the following context that informs the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. The background for UG's activities within the CATALISI initiative are grounded within the context of the education system in Poland, which largely retains a centralized character. The higher education system has experienced a lack of investment. Poland's expenditure on research and development (R&D) is significantly below the EU average (around 1.4% of GDP vs. the EU average of 2.22%), leading to insufficient funding for research projects, infrastructure, and competitive salaries for academics. In effect, this is compounded by low salaries and limited career opportunities in academia force many talented researchers and young scientists to seek better-paid jobs in the private sector or abroad, resulting in a significant outflow of talent.

There is a historical prioritisation of teaching over research and research is also challenged by competing independent institutions (universities, research centres, private companies) that often work in isolation, which hinders interdisciplinary collaboration and a unified national research policy, making it difficult to compete with larger, consolidated Western European universities. The system is also quite bureaucratic, with considerable administrative barriers. Researchers face significant bureaucracy and support needs when applying for EU funding, most notable a lack of professional administrative support for grant writing and post-award management.

Improving research quality emphasizes publications in high-impact international journals over longer term research excellence or societal collaboration for impact. The funding system has been criticized for not sufficiently incentivizing high-impact international research or interdisciplinary cooperation. A lack of established international networks and linguistic challenges has contributed to further marginalizing Polish Universities in the European Research Area. Despite efforts to attract international students, barriers such as a limited number of English-taught programs, inefficient visa procedures, and language barriers in daily life hinder progress. UG described a fear of losing intellectual property. Insufficient support and oversight in shaping a scientist's career trajectory was also highlighted. A lack of a UG brand management strategy with effective customer relationships was also noted. A lack of innovation readiness level is compounded by a lack of understanding of market needs. Improving experiences with business and relationships between researchers is vital to them.

Secondly, UG initially articulated the following issues they wished to address in response to the context articulated above.

- They wish to deepen cooperation with business and community stakeholders, UG recognizes public engagement and outreach as a strategic priority to foster societal impact and strengthen the university's role as a driver of innovation and collaboration.
- A way forward is to promote citizen science to ensure that academic outputs address real-world challenges and enabling active participation of the public in research activities.
- They will pursue an intensification of cooperation with companies to ensure that UG students are collaborating with the private sector and engaged in immersive and experiential co-problem solving.
- A way forward is to integrate academic work with societal needs by encouraging students to prepare bachelor's and master's theses in collaboration with business partners, directly addressing industry and community challenges.

- They wish to improve their commitment to sustainability through a survey to assess need, initiate circular economy measures such as book sharing schemes, and engage in promoting the idea among students, professors and staff.

Transformational Pathways

At the beginning of the initiative, UG performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

UG focussed on 3 main domains and 3 intervention areas:

- Research careers and talent support:
 - Recognition of qualifications and research careers.
- Research modus operandi:
 - Public engagement with and outreach to society to solve social challenges.
- Finance:
 - Sustainability in campus operations

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where UCC supported UG to adopt the recommendations of the External Acceleration Board (EAB). UCC and the EAB noted that objectives were too general and lacked clear, measurable outcomes. It was suggested that the plan would benefit from more specific actions, defined timelines, and robust monitoring mechanisms. Greater emphasis on external stakeholder involvement and clearer resource allocation was also recommended. UG subsequently refocused around formative input from UCC and EAB feedback in relation to their activity and performance indicators. Subsequently, UG's transformation pathway was much more clearly defined and strategically aligned, with clear objectives, measurable outputs, and strong operational commitment.

Transformation Focus		
Public Engagement		Sustainability
Participate in IP&I Week to promote public engagement among different stakeholders. Organising an Intellectual Property & Innovation Week with external stakeholders to showcase and familiarize them with the concept intellectual property, open science and science for society. UG will compile notes from the event and recommendations on ways to create, maintain and promote public engagement at the university; discussions based on notes will lead to the creation of a set of recommendations.	Create customer journey map. Training on building relationships with customers. Introduce an integrated training system for UG employees. Learning to identify commercial services.	Diagnosis of potential/capacity in the context of sustainability. Check needs of the environment, and design forms of education, not vice versa. Organizing events to showcase and transfer good sustainability practices to stakeholders within the socio-economic ecosystem. Promoting resource sharing through initiatives such as co-sharing of books among staff and students, fostering a culture of sustainability and collaboration. Leveraging digital tools to disseminate knowledge, including publishing webinars in Open Access and sharing recommendations for future actions.
Have a support centre for scientists. Train the staff to increase the cooperation with business. Monitoring of employees' professional qualifications and skills. Regular meetings with entrepreneurs, ESG Manager post graduate studies.		

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TABLE 9: UG TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Results (Outputs and Outcomes)

UG has pursued a dual objective aiming of improving its commitment to sustainability and the institution's relationship with external stakeholders across the Quadruple Helix, with a particular emphasis on the private sector. Through co-learning with CATALISI partners this evolved into promoting/embedding citizen science in the university. This led to clear and straightforward activities and indicators, albeit at the expense of possibly a more ambitious set of objectives. Furthermore, as also indicated by the EAB, it wasn't initially clear how UG planned on integrating the activities, in its Action Plan and Transformational Pathway, for long-term impact, as several indicators seemed to be quite short-term in their scope and self-selective. The progress UG made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
UG 1	In an attempt to strengthen linkages and collaboration between UG and the business community, develop and pilot a process by Dec 2025 whereby UG undergraduate and postgraduate thesis can be completed by UG students in tandem with regional enterprise and innovation partners.	UG-Business Thesis Pilot		Y	Workshop completed. Pilot up and running in Economics Faculty. Potential value-add as pilot now being examined by other faculties.
UG 2	To actively support public engagement and building strategic relationships with regional business stakeholders, create and embed an Intellectual Property and Innovation week based on stakeholder needs, at UG in April 2025.	IP & Innovation week		Y	Innovation week developed and held 1-3 April 2025. Follow up to see if surveyed conducted with business on needs and further enhancement.
UG 3	To help promote and embed Citizen Science at UG, leverage the Catalisi and Living Lab methodologies to create and launch a Citizen Science Lab at UG by November 2025.	Citizen Science Lab		Y	In progress, positive legacy post-project. Follow up re governance, ownership etc.

FIGURE 13: UG STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

UG's engagement with the CATALISI Model and its Acceleration Services, was at times not well harmonized, resulting in an emergent level of alignment with the model and methodology. However, the university achieved academic and economic impact thanks to its wider structural policy developments which reinforced complimentary measures undertaken through CATALISI. Of note is the initiation of deeper collaboration with the QH, particularly businesses and the establishment of systems for Business Student Thesis to respond to external need. The UG team were moderately attuned to the changes suggested by the EAB and UCC throughout the project. They embarked on a concise set of activities that initially lacked strategic direction but significantly improved through dialogue with UCC and the EAB feedback.

Summary

UG underwent a positive and necessary transformational journey as part of the CATALISI project. At times it appeared that the activity across their action plan was siloed in nature, depending on what part of the organisation owned the action. In addition, in 2024 in particular, upon adding new personnel to the project, progress seemed to stall so it is commendable that the UG Team refocused and made measurable progress in 2025, in particular.

UG's 2023-24 action plan was strategic in nature and detailed clear ambition around a seaports action group, connecting business with student theses, a baseline survey and knowledge day. However, no KPIs had been identified initially. From working with UCC, taking on board feedback from EAB and by utilisation of acceleration services, learning from other partners (and developing collaborations with KTU), UG made progress on their change agenda. Action Plans 2 and 3 saw UG refocus to 7 key objectives and UG completed the

project with 3 strategic KPIs, that are impact and outcome focused, strategic in nature and clearly owned as well as being embedded within the university, beyond the business faculty.

- The transformation pathway is strategically aligned and sequenced, after a period of internal consolidation and focus. Their KPIs are focussed on achieving activities and could benefit from an outcome's orientation.
- However, there is limited clarity on how the transformation activities feed into research; the orientation around student education and preparation through immersion in problem solving with businesses is a step change towards impact focussed research.
- The focus on sustainability measures is a positive development, which could be extended through an interdisciplinary approach linking with other faculties across the institution to advance sustainability research with businesses. It will be important to translate ambitions as an institution into specific actions and measurable outcomes.
- A university-wide entrepreneurship strategy has been developed which is an important step in creating a more coordinated institutional approach.
- A legacy impact from the CATALISI initiative has been the establishment of UG's first Citizen Science Lab. Embedding this post-project will see UG work closer with society in delivering Scientific impact in the region. Consortium working will allow UG to advance its goals for sustained transformation.

In summary, as a result of CATALISI, UG is moving from a more inward-facing transformation to one grounded in citizen science and social impact. Continued collaboration with other CATALISI partners into the future, especially with KTU is suggested regarding Citizen Science, continuing shared initiatives.

3.1.5. Case Study 5: UCC

Overview

University College Cork (UCC), located in Cork, Ireland, is a leading university established in 1845. It offers a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs to its 25,000 students and is known for its strong focus on research and innovation. The campus is modern and close to Cork city centre. UCC is recognized for its commitment to societal engagement and sustainability and is ranked the 4th most sustainable university in the world according to UI Green Metric. The university values the relationship between students and lecturers, creating a supportive learning environment.

University College Cork sees research, education, and engagement as interconnected elements that can drive societal progress and economic growth. They are committed to make a positive impact through its research and innovation (R&I) efforts. Their aim is to transform HEIs towards a more financially sustainable research and innovation ecosystem that enhances excellence and world-class research. UCC recognizes the need for innovative funding approaches amidst new demands, such as the green and digital transition, and seeks to address challenges like over-reliance on limited funding sources, brain drain, and fragmented support systems for researchers. Through its Community Engagement activities such as Living Labs, UCC engages stakeholders to co-create solutions, enabling strategic

investment, institutional autonomy, and deeper societal collaboration to future-proof its research and innovation capabilities.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, UCC highlighted the following context that informs the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. UCC operates in a higher education system where research capacity is experiencing underfunding, inadequate infrastructure, and an over-reliance on research for industry-oriented funding. These issues create significant challenges for attracting and retaining talent and maintaining research quality. State funding per student has fallen dramatically over the last decade, leading to overall underinvestment in the sector compared to international peers. Ireland lags in per-student investment and higher education research activity rankings. This creates a major risk to sector sustainability and international competitiveness. There is a significant lack of capital investment, with insufficient funds allocated for maintaining existing facilities or building new ones. A large percentage of the physical space requires major repair or replacement. The sector struggles to attract and retain high-quality researchers because it cannot compete with private sector salaries. This is particularly detrimental to early-career researchers, whose careers are often shaped by short-term, precarious contracts. There is relatively over-reliance on industry funding, and this can lead to an unbalanced research agenda, prioritizing commercially valuable, short-term projects over long-term, fundamental, or curiosity-driven research. This focus on immediate "impact" can also fragment research efforts and compromise academic independence and the public-good mission of universities.

UCC highlighted:

- The ratio of students to staff is significantly higher in Ireland (e.g., 23:1) than the OECD and EU averages (e.g., 15:1), placing immense pressure on academic staff and limiting the time available for research.
- Bureaucracy and Lack of Autonomy: Institutions often face overly prescriptive performance indicators and a high degree of micromanagement from the state, which can stifle innovation.
- Low research investment for research and innovation.
- Over-reliance on small number of large-scale research centres in UCC creates financial risk.
- Research income often covers only direct project costs, with inadequate institutional overheads to support the full cost of running research projects, such as administrative and support services.
- Lack of mechanisms to retain overhead funds for strategic initiatives or capacity-building efforts, limiting the institution's ability to invest in long-term sustainability.
- Brain drain and attracting and sustaining a pipeline of research talent.
- Underdeveloped pre- and post-award grant support for researchers.
- External funding agencies increasingly influence research priorities, limiting HEIs ability to pursue institutionally driven research agendas.
- There is a disconnect between research systems and societal actors, funding bodies, and policymakers.

Secondly, UCC initially articulated the following issues they wished to address in response to the context articulated above. Given the above context, UCC made a strategic decision to prioritise one Intervention Area – Sustainability in research and finance. They aimed to:

- Explore, identify and articulate financing issues for sustainability in research, particularly detailing framework conditions, barriers and enablers.
- Co-Create a revised Overhead Model. Advocate for greater institutional autonomy by influencing funding policies and creating systems that support more diverse and institutionally determined research priorities.
- Advance a strong Research Culture, focusing on strengthening research integrity through societal engagement and positioning to advance research sustainability and financing.

Transformation Pathway

At the beginning of the initiative, UCC performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

UCC focused on 1 cross-cutting domain and intervention area:

- Finance:
 - Sustainability in campus operations

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where they adopted the recommendations of the External Acceleration Board (EAB). The EAB noted that the Action Plan was strong in its clear focus on financial sustainability, alignment with UCC's strategic plan, and comprehensive coverage of research funding, infrastructure, and talent retention. UCC engaged strongly in the Living Lab methodology. However, the EAB noted that while the plan was robust it would benefit from more targeted actions and improved monitoring. UCC subsequently refocused around input from the EAB, and subsequently UCC's transformation pathway was much more clearly defined and strategically aligned, with clear objectives, measurable outputs, and strong operational commitment.

Transformation Focus		
Financial Sustainability		
Actively involve the quadruple helix stakeholders. "Living Lab" approach: stakeholders from academia, business, public administration, and civil society collaborate to identify challenges and co-create solutions.	Building a strategic model of income allocation that balances the need for financial sustainability with the flexibility to invest in long-term goals, such as talent retention and support for Open Science initiatives.	Advocate for greater institutional autonomy by influencing funding policies and creating systems that support more diverse and institutionally determined research priorities.

TABLE 10: UCC TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Results (Outputs and Outcomes)

UCC has retained a narrow and focused approach to its Action Plan and Transformational Pathway from the very beginning of CATALISI. Throughout the initiative, the UCC team took an introspective approach to modelling and adapting its activities by both integrating the

EAB's suggestions as well as incorporating the findings and learnings originating from the Formative Bilateral meetings, which it had the opportunity of conducting with each implementing partner. The progress UCC made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
UCC 1	UCC will embed the Catalisi Acceleration Services, in particular the Living Lab approach and learnings from other implementing partners in 2023 and 2024, to examine and provide strategic implementable solutions to the sustainability of research financing at the University.	Embed Catalisi methodology including Living Lab Approach		Y	Living Lab established at UCC, utilised to examine the sustainability of finance issue, and co create solutions. New income streams in place and additional research funding won using the approach.
UCC 2	Supporting the sustainability of research financing, Co Create and implement a revised overhead model in relation to indirect research costs in 2025 which will serve the University to deliver its research and innovation strategy to 2028.	Co created revised overhead model		Y	Revised overhead model devised and implemented university-wide.
UCC 3	With the overall aim of supporting the sustainability of research financing, UCC will leverage the Catalisi methodology to co-create and pilot new income streams in 2024 and 2025, such that these are embedded at the University by the end of the project.	New income streams embedded		Y	UCC has additionally deepened its engagement with the EU Urban Initiative, INTEREGG, WIDERA, MSCA and Erasmus+ grants. UCC won £1m Welcome Trust grant on research culture leveraging Catalisi methodology. UCC also pursuing KER in relation to approach to evaluation and impact assessment.

FIGURE 14: UCC STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

UCC interacted especially with the Living Lab and Capacity Building & Outreach Acceleration Services, maintaining a high level of alignment with the CATALISI model and methodology. These aspects proved to be key enablers in allowing the institution to pursue the desired change. UCC has ensured long-term academic, social and economic impact thanks to, respectively: embedding CATALISI acceleration services in the university and engaging with other HEIs for future research endeavours, developing a robust participatory approach, securing funding and implementing a new revised overhead model for research funding.

Summary

UCC progressed a positive transformational journey through the CATALISI project. As noted by the EAB, UCC took a very focused approach to affecting change and preferred to scale deep in relation to the sustainability of research financing, as opposed to scaling wide across multiple intervention areas simultaneously. Given UCC's dual role as implementor and evaluator, this proved to be a pragmatic approach. UCC's 2023-24 action plan saw 7 goals and corresponding KPIs. Through effective use of acceleration services, adapting to EAB feedback, learning from the other partners and leveraging internal expertise, UCC's 2025 action plans were more focused, strategic and accountable in nature. UCC concluded the project with 3 strategic, meaningful performance indicators reflecting a change in research governance structures as set out, whilst also delivering social, scientific and economic impacts for the University.

- UCC refined its transformation strategy to focus on sustainable research funding, internal capacity-building, and strategic engagement, with clear alignment to institutional priorities.
- A strong culture of co-creation is evident through stakeholder workshops, real-time evaluation, and design thinking methods that have fostered inclusive dialogue and secured buy-in from academic leadership.
- The acceleration services have been effectively leveraged to strengthen internal capabilities and community engagement, contributing to a mature and well-managed transformation process.
- UCC demonstrates strong commitment to quadruple helix collaboration, excelling in co-creation with CATALISI partners across academia, government, industry, and civil society.

- Financial sustainability efforts could leverage UCC's strong positioning in environmental sustainability, to create an even more unified and strategic approach.
- A particularly impactful step is the creation and integration of a strategic research fund within the Vice President for Research's office, supporting long-term sustainability.
- The transformation pathway is well integrated into institutional planning, with clear objectives and strong senior leadership support.
- UCC should expand engagement via its European University Alliance and City-Labs approach with local authorities, businesses, and civil society to support innovation, funding discussions, and long-term ecosystem integration.
- UCC's laser focus on the sustainability of research financing allowed the team to focus strategically and bring about impactful university-wide change in research governance. The new overhead model in relation to the collection and distribution of indirect cost of research, will position the university well for future research growth, aligned with its strategy. Furthermore, UCC successfully leveraged the CATALISI methodology to help secure €1.3m in competitively won research funding, to accelerate work on research culture - a good example of delivered direct economic impact.

In summary, through responding to the main EAB recommendations, UCC took extra care in focusing on long-term sustainability of their activities by drawing out plans for the further maintenance of the changes initiated in CATALISI. By integrating the CATALISI Living Lab approach, Co-creating a Revised Overhead Model and identifying/embedding new income streams, it is well positioned to pursue long-term and impactful institutional transformation into the foreseeable future.

3.1.6. Case Study 6: AUTH

Overview

The Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) is the largest university in Greece (over 80,000 students in all), located in the heart of Thessaloniki. Established in 1925, The university's main campus includes 10 faculties with 40 schools. It has 4000 students and 82 departments and laboratories. The University is one of the oldest in Greece and has a wide range of faculties and subject areas. AUTH is publicly funded. It is a teaching intensive university. Research is a priority but competes with the demands of a traditional teaching university.

AUTH offers a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs, with instruction primarily in Greek, though there are courses available in English, French, German, and Italian. The university is renowned for its research output and academic excellence, making it a significant educational institution in Greece and the broader region.

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki aims to become an innovative university that prioritizes collaboration, inclusivity, and the well-being of its community. The university envisions itself as a hub for research and education that emphasizes citizen engagement, safety, and open access to knowledge. AUTH aims to foster a secure and supportive environment for research, thus attracting and retaining top talent.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, AUTH highlighted the following context that informs the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. The context for CATALISI is the Faculty of Health Sciences, School of Medicine. The school has technology and legal units. The Medical Physics & Digital Innovation Lab, one of the Medicine Laboratory's, is an ENOLL accredited Living Lab. It leads the CATALISI initiative in AUTH. A PI or a Professor, leads large research groups, and leads each Laboratory. Research is funded in the university primarily through EU grants, which they compete for. National funding is very limited and very competitive. The reliance on EU funding means research is organised around EU priorities, not necessarily Greek. The economic crisis in Greece is a major contextual factor as it has made it difficult for national funding for research, due to other competing priorities for the government. The more established researchers tend to get funded, if you are less established, you find it more difficult. Government tends to make macro level policies for the sector, and the system is very bureaucratic. In the university there is no central research leadership office and no university research strategy, or a national strategy. Each Medicine Lab for example has its own research strategy.

AUTH is a teaching intensive university in a system with limited time for research, and limited research funding and a staff who wish to address national/ local Greek research priorities. Open Science and Fair Principles are a way to encourage collaboration across academia, industry, public authorities, and citizen groups. When these groups are invited to participate in the research and innovation process, creativity and trust in science increases. This engagement process leads to greater transparency in the research process, greater potential impact of research, more efficient research processes and opportunities for global scientific collaboration.

Producing Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) is a way to provide interactive asynchronous learning, potentially if designed well, it can support face to face time with lecturers. This can potentially free up teaching time for research. If MOOCs and other technology assisted modalities can free up staff time for research, the AUTH focus on MOOCs becomes more strategic. This can also attract research talent to locate in Greece, if the system is more supportive of research time, thus contributing to solving brain drain issues. The goal is to use MOOC development to improve teaching quality, this can also attract academics who have research driven and informed teaching approaches. Research-led teaching describes how existing research underpins curriculum content and can be a modality for improving research quality and its impact.

Secondly, AUTH initially articulated the following issues they wished to address in response to the context articulated above.

- Digitization with a particular focus on promoting the usage of MOOCs, especially within the Medical School. This initiative is especially targeted at the Medical School, where the integration of MOOCs could offer significant benefits in terms of accessibility and flexibility in learning and freeing up time for research. It also broadens access to high-quality educational content and supports lifelong learning and teaching practices.
- Mainstreaming of Open Science & Sustainability in Research with an emphasis on facilitating Fair Data & IP Sharing. Implementing Open Science principles and data sharing practices into its research culture, AUTH will develop greater levels of societal collaboration and transparency. Their goal is to foster a more sustainable and inclusive research environment.
- Living labs lack mechanisms for recognizing qualifications and their contributions to Open Science. They have identified a gap in provision, a need to provide a credential to users of their Living Labs, which include researchers but also other QH partners,

including citizens involved in citizen science projects. The goal here is to improve the science and society interface through bridging the gap between for example technology discovery and innovation and its realisation and implementation. All users of the LL will be able to avail of this credential. By developing a certification procedure for Living Labs and citizen science research, AUTH seeks to formalize and standardize these practices across European HEIs, making them more impactful.

Transformational Pathway

At the beginning of the initiative, AUTH performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

AUTH focussed on 3 main domains and 5 intervention areas:

- Research careers and talent support:
 - Recognition of qualifications and research careers.
 - Reform of research assessment.
 - Digitization of higher education sector.
- Research modus operandi:
 - Mainstreaming of open science and digitization of research.
- Finance:
 - Sustainability in research.

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where they adopted the recommendations of UCC and the External Acceleration Board (EAB). The AUTH Action Plan was recognized for its ambitious short- and medium-term objectives, especially in integrating Living Labs, citizen science, and digital transformation into teaching and research. However, the plan was seen as too broad, raising concerns about feasibility given resource and bureaucratic constraints. It was recommended they narrow the focus, developing actionable steps for medium- and long-term goals, and establishing clear KPIs. AUTH subsequently refocused around input from UCC and the EAB and subsequently AUTH's transformation pathway was much more clearly defined and strategically aligned, with clear objectives, measurable outputs, and strong operational commitment.

Transformation Focus		
MOOC	Open Science	LL Certification
Acknowledge and reward non-traditional research outputs. Development of a certification for Living Labs and citizen science research. Financial and medical insurance against incidents during research projects, experiments, and focus groups. Accessible dissertations and datasets.	Identify and implement tools, platforms, or frameworks that facilitate the collection, management, analysis, and sharing of data in a transparent and fair manner. Promote awareness and accessibility, bridging the gap between data availability and utilization.	Centralized database for managing IP and collaborative projects and research awareness. Establish IP Policies and Guidelines that outline the rights, responsibilities and processes for IP Sharing.

TABLE 11: AUTH TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Results (Outputs and Outcomes)

AUTH presented a very ambitious set of objectives from the beginning of the CATALISI project. Promoting a new accreditation system in the institution, considering the challenging national and cultural HE ecosystem, will prove an extremely impactful change. As already noted by the EAB, AUTH's engagement with Living Lab methodologies positions the institution as a pioneer in its local academic environment. That said, this will depend on gathering and maintaining engagement with QH stakeholders which, as the EAB feedback suggests, was less developed in the beginning of their Action Plan and Transformational Pathway implementation. Finally, the promotion and mainstreaming of Open Science and Citizen Science, and the objectives achieved through the project indicate a strong commitment to pursuing these goals after the end of CATALISI. The progress AUTH made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
AUTH 1	Advance efforts to create a transparent and equitable framework for research assessment and qualification recognition within the academic community, by completing a thorough mapping and review (in 2024) of existing university policies and processes related to qualification acknowledgment, professional progression, and reward mechanisms at AUTH.	Comprehensive Review		Y	Review and mapping exercise completed. Also expanded beyond the Medical Department to include both the IT and Law departments as well. 10 policy areas and procedures were identified for revision and/or alignment.
AUTH 2	Promoting flexible and open access learning, integrate Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) into AUTH's medical department by December 2025 through the provision of 3 or more high quality MOOCs which help to modernise AUTH's medical learning, expand lifelong pathways, and support open and accessible higher education in Europe.	Integration of MOOCs		Y	AUTH has a plan in place to integrate three MOOCs addressing themes of digital health innovation, medical technology, and responsible research practices.
AUTH 3	To aid mainstreaming of Open Science, promoting open data sharing, FAIR data management, and ethical research practices, develop and introduce (in 2025) a lecture on data sharing and openness within the Medical Department's Innovation Course, which helps to embed Open Science principles into undergraduate education.	Lecture on open data, FAIR data		Y	Lecture developed and introduced in tandem with AUTH's Technology Transfer Office.

FIGURE 15: AUTH STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

AUTH initiated an organisational culture transformation through demonstrating and modelling the potential of distributed leadership, stakeholder participation and grassroots led innovation that improves the university / science and society interface through bridging the gap between technology discovery and innovation and its realisation and implementation *with* societal partners. Its aim to transform teaching and learning, is oriented towards retaining and attracting research talent (addressing 'brain drain'), freeing up time for research, and improving teaching quality through research led teaching.

AUTH's engagement with the Living Lab Acceleration Service, as to be expected considering their objectives, was very strong from the beginning of the project; exploitation of the Transformational Pathway and the Capacity Building and Outreach services were also noted, demonstrating strong alignment with the CATALISI model and methodology. Furthermore, the institution is on a course to achieve strong academic and economic impact thanks to, respectively: the progress made in recognitions and qualifications, integrating MOOCs in the Medical Department and the mainstreaming of open Science in research.

Summary

AUTH underwent a positive transformational journey as part of the CATALISI project. Their review on research assessment, integration of MOOCs and progress on Open Science (data) are important to them given the sheer size of the university (80,000 students) and their local context. Indeed, the 3 areas of intervention serve to help transcend the faculty structures that are so apparent at AUTH. While the changes were affected from the medical department in

particular, the fact that they have been completed will serve as a catalysts to other parts of the university.

AUTHs 2023-24 action plan identified 6 KPIs which were largely operational measures relating to reviewing information, mapping activity, counting students as well as one off events. By being open to change, use of the acceleration services (in particular the living lab methodology which AUTH has great expertise in), and by learning from other partners, taking on board UCC's formative assessment approach and the feedback from the EAB, it is evident that AUTH accelerated progress during the project. The 2025 version of the action plan was far more specific and AUTH concludes the project with 3 KPIs (co-created (with UCC), which are impact and outcome focused, strategic in nature and meaningful. Importantly, the KPIs can be replicated and scaled elsewhere within the University.

- Given that change processes, such as the CATALISI initiative, are only possible in AUTH, if they take a bottom-up approach, feasibility and continued successful implementation could benefit from a connection between individual initiatives and wider institutional decision-making and planning for implementation and resource allocation.
- The KPIs in the future as the work progresses would be strengthened by incorporating institutional embedding and stakeholder impact. In addition, a focus on fewer, actions will improve overall coherence and implementation feasibility.
- The areas being pursued are strategic in intent and designed to contribute to and advance University wider objectives, such as technology enhanced learning, open science and societal participation in research and innovation. However, it is vital to see integration of the transformation activities as needing an anchor in governance and long-term strategic planning.
- AUTH's emphasis on certifications and accreditation in Citizen Science projects is a unique and ambitious initiative. The concept of certifying participation in Living Labs through innovative qualification frameworks is pioneering and positions AUTH as a potential leader in this emerging area.
- Risks include the ability to deliver without top-down partnerships, and to mitigate this risk, the buy-in of established sponsors internally and important lever to help ensure smooth delivery of the objectives. In addition, most of the change was initiated at medical department level and a challenge for AUTH is to embed transformations cross-university.

AUTH successfully delivered against stated aims. Through a focused approach within the medical department, the AUTH team has successfully delivered Massive Open Online Courses at the University for the first time. This is transformational given the sheer size of the University and a very positive social impact for the region as the legacy is the promotion of flexible and open access learning for society. In summary, the AUTH team has proven very responsive in integrating both the EAB's and UCC's, feedback throughout the initiative. We believe that they are well positioned to pursue long-term and impactful institutional change into the foreseeable future.

3.1.7. Case Study 7: AUMC

Overview

Amsterdam University Medical Centre (AUMC) located in Amsterdam, Netherlands, is a leading medical centre formed by the merger of the Academic Medical Centre (AMC) and VU University Medical Centre (VUMC) in 2018. The AUMC CATALISI team is located at the VUMC location. It is affiliated with both the University of Amsterdam and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. AUMC is well-known for its comprehensive healthcare services, education, and cutting-edge research. The Amsterdam Medical University aims to become a forward-thinking, globally interconnected Higher Education Institution (HEI) that champions responsible and ethical research practices. They are committed to reforming research assessment to better recognize qualifications and research careers, while fostering a research culture rooted in integrity and inclusivity. Their focus on Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR), research integrity, and open science highlights their dedication to transparency and ethical standards. With expertise in gender equality, inclusiveness, and sustainability in research, the university also seeks to mainstream open science and digitization efforts. By embedding these values into their policies and educational frameworks, such as through mandatory PhD courses and established codes of conduct, the Amsterdam Medical University is positioning itself as a leader in promoting a sustainable, inclusive, and ethical research environment.

Theory of Change Narrative

Firstly, VUMC highlighted the following context that informs the rationale underpinning their CATALISI organisational change process. In the background of CATALISI, as described by VUMC, is a context of declining government funding for research and innovation, including cuts to research councils and grants for researchers. This has led to the cancellation of important research projects and concerns about future prosperity and competitiveness. There is an over reliance on temporary or short-term contracts for academic staff, especially postdocs, has increased significantly, eroding job security and negatively impacting working conditions. This contributes to high work pressure across the system. There are concerns about growing political influence on the content and direction of scientific research and education, threatening academic freedom. There are also structural problems in its reward system that disadvantage scholars from working-class or lower-income backgrounds, and the representation of female professors also remains below the EU average.

CATALISI in AUMC is an initiative led by the Medical Faculty's Department of Ethics, Law and Humanities, but targeted at both the Free University of Amsterdam and the Amsterdam University Medical Centre. The Medical Centre is an amalgamation of two medical centres into one, now the largest in the Netherlands. The two parts are separate, the Free University and the Medical Centre, however they have a shared medical faculty. Researchers/Academics are hired or lined managed in either the Free University or the Amsterdam Medical Centre.

The Free University has its roots as a Christian university, so it sees itself as 'standing for something'. It began as a private university, so this sometimes excludes it from funding opportunities that public universities have. It has a 25% migrant population, which sets it apart from typical mainstream Dutch Universities. They have a focus on cultivating diversity and allowing multiple identities to flourish. It sees itself as being inclusive and progressive.

Importantly the culture of the university is very dialogical. However, the Medical Centre has a relatively competitive culture and can often be hierarchical. This is typical of Medical Centres, especially one as nationally significant as theirs. In contrast, the Free University Governing Board values dialogue, and conducts frequent debate sessions with staff and students. (This contributes to building cohesion in a diverse university). The National System is quiet hands off comparatively. Its role is to offer checks on quality of universities but

otherwise it does not overly interfere. The Netherlands has a Dutch Code of Conduct (2018) signed by all the universities. Each university is expected to have training, structures etc for this.

They are a research-intensive university and centre, with an emphasis on research over teaching. The Centre is an 'academic hospital' and a former Rector of the Free University became a Professor of Research Integrity based in the Philosophy Department, the first such appointment. He acted as a bridge between the University and the Centre. There was / is no infrastructure between the two institutions. The CATALISI project is helping to create shared infrastructure between the 2 institutions.

Some see efforts around research culture as bringing in a layer of additional bureaucracy that affects academic freedom, especially ethics reviews and standards, open access etc. But they do also understand that the quality of research needs to improve. They are taking a long implementation strategy for this reason, incrementally improving things such as using champions in each of the faculties. The ultimate goal is to make research trustworthy. However, they see that staff have a developing level of knowledge and there is a need to stimulate a change in research culture in various departments/faculties regarding research quality. There is especially a need to embed sustainable training and education in research quality for students and staff.

Secondly, AUMC initially articulated the following issues they wished to address in response to the context articulated above.

- Their theory of change focuses on the sustainable embedding of Research Integrity (RI) education and the transformation of research culture, with targeted actions for reforming research assessment, recognizing diverse research careers, and strengthening transversal skills. They plan to continuously refine their approach towards long-term impact, especially to increase public trust in the quality of research, leading to a strong research-societal interface.
- Over the short term they will achieve progress through quantitative and qualitative improvement in researcher awareness and understanding of Responsible Conduct of Research and its components (eg stimulating a positive Research Culture), leading to medium term incremental change in research culture and ultimately over the longer term embedding research integrity as part of the practices and professional identity of their researchers.

Transformation Pathway

At the beginning of the initiative, AUTH performed a comprehensive stakeholder mapping exercise and conducted a SWOT analysis (D1.1 Needs Assessment) to inform the initial development of its Transformation Pathway and Action Plan (D1.2 Action Plans) and initial KPI's.

AUMC focussed on 1 main domain and 2 intervention areas:

- Research careers and talent support:
 - Recognition of qualifications and research careers.
 - Reform of research assessment.

The initial version of their Action Plan was revised as part of the Evaluation and Impact Assessment (WP4), where they adopted the recommendations of UCC and the External Acceleration Board (EAB). The plan was praised for its clear structure, alignment with

institutional priorities, and the involvement of multiple stakeholders—such as RI coordinators, academic staff, and policy makers—in both the design and implementation phases, fostering a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement. It was noted that the plan would benefit from more detailed sequencing of actions, clearer KPIs, and a stronger link to the co-creative Quadruple Helix approach. It was also recommended expanding the monitoring framework and ensuring that research culture changes are measurable and inclusive. AUMC subsequently refocused around input from UCC and the EAB and subsequently the transformation pathway was much more clearly defined and strategically aligned, with clear objectives, measurable outputs, and strong operational commitment.

Transformation Focus	
Recognition of qualifications and research careers	Reform of research assessment.
<p>Offer a network for exchange on trainings for PHD's and improve training quality and teacher quality (Re)design and embed trainings for PhD students and supervisors/senior staff</p> <p>Offer workshops to departments in various disciplines to stimulate RCR</p> <p>Increase awareness on stimulating a positive Research Culture</p> <p>Changes in researcher assessment (recognition & reward policies).</p> <p>Redevelop & implement PhD and supervisor training.</p>	<p>Offer a learning pathway on RCR in the organization that aligns with changing researcher assessment policies</p> <p>Work with relevant policymakers and support staff in the faculties to make RCR more relevant if it is aligned with researcher assessment initiatives</p> <p>Start and sustain the Research Integrity and Open Science Centre Amsterdam (RIOS)</p>

TABLE 12: AUMC TRANSFORMATION FOCUS.

Summary of Results

AUMC has undertaken an ambitious set of objectives but was able to focus their approach and not allow the ambitious nature of their goals to disperse their attention, which led to the creation of a streamlined set of activities and KPIs. That said, as noted by UCC and the EAB, the details surrounding the long-term sustainability of some of their actions was highlighted. The progress AUMC made in achieving its KPI's are outlined below:

Ref	Final Draft (Strategic) Key Performance Indicators	Short Name	RAG Status	Delivered	Commentary - Evidence
AUMC 1	To strategically embed the responsible conduct of research education for supervisors at UMC and VU by developing, implementing and monitoring the Mpowering Responsible Supervision course by December 2025.	Mpowering		Y	Course developed and embedded at both institutions
AUMC 2	With the aim of embedding Research Integrity and Open Science conduct a comprehensive start of the art with regard to all the Research Integrity training available at UMC and VU in 2024. Through the establishment of the Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science create a physical and virtual hub of resources for PhD students, supervisors and academic staff alike in 2025. Support the sustainability of this work through the establishment of networks and communities of practice in 2025.	Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science		Y	State of the Art completed, Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science established. Resources centralised and networks in place for targeted groups.
AUMC 3	Within the aim of fostering a positive research culture at both VU and UMC, develop a survey tool in relation to deepening the understanding of research culture - perceptions, experiences and needs in 2025. Conduct the survey, analyse the results and make policy recommendations by December 2025, that may be considered for implementation in both institutions.	Research Culture Survey		Y	Survey developed, undertaken and completed. (Not only in VU & UMC but also in collaboration with UJl and UCC). The results were analysed and have been summarised in policy recommendations.

FIGURE 16: AUMC STRATEGIC KPI TOOL.

AUMC alignment with the CATALISI model and methodology was strong and well embedded, AUMC proved to be extremely responsive in integrating the feedback by both

the EAB, as well as UCC, which produced, throughout the project, an even stronger Action Plan and Transformational Pathway.

Summary

AUMC pursued a very positive, well-thought out and clear transformation journey through the Catalisi project. Their focus was clear and concise from the outset, and this was set out in the first action plan from 2023-24, where 12 KPI were identified. These KPIs, albeit somewhat operational, helped to bring focus and structure to their activities in the early stages of the project. AUMC participated fully in all activities across the project and integrated the acceleration services as appropriate. AUMC took on board the formative approach to evaluation from UCC and the feedback from EAB and were keen to collaborate with partners throughout the project. This was borne out by their collaboration with UCC and UJI on research culture. In addition, AUMC's clarity of purpose was such that the team were comfortable to innovate throughout the project in order to advance the change agenda. This is evidenced by the development and delivery of a theatre play to advance knowledge on research integrity. AUMC leave the project with 3 strategic, well-defined KPIs which are impact focused and clearly owned. AUMC successfully delivered what they set out to do and succeeded in embedding their changes across the university, while cleverly anchoring them in the newly established Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science. Post project, they are well positioned in these areas for 2026 and beyond.

- The AUMC transformational agenda benefited from being clear and focused from the outset, centring on embedding Responsible Conduct of Research (RCR) training, with well-defined short-medium- and long-term objectives.
- The initiative is strongly aligned with national integrity frameworks and is well integrated into institutional culture and educational programmes.
- Implementation has been effective, thanks to committed leadership, active researcher engagement, and strategic use of capacity-building and change leadership acceleration services.
- An emphasis on cultural change, especially through plans to evaluate behavioral shifts, shows a commitment to values-driven transformation beyond procedural compliance.
- Co-creation is a core feature, with ongoing stakeholder involvement ensuring the strategy remains relevant and adaptable. Internally, the pathway is coherent and widely owned, supported by clear KPIs and structured planning.
- Going forward KPIs could evolve to transcend their procedural compliance orientation to reflect the real-world long-term impact of VUMC initiatives, especially European wide learning and VUMC as a leader of shared standards and practices for interdisciplinary European research teams.
- Their hands on leadership commitment enabled them to identify how to leverage CATALISI strategically and especially the use of acceleration services as a change management vehicle.
- Cumulative leadership direction prior to and during CATALISI was focused on organizational culture as a key driver of transformation over more managerialist approaches, which is noted as a key strength.
- Research culture and integrity have the potential to transcend aspects such as career development and researcher performance, to also consider societal engagement

across the quadruple helix, leveraging a broader ecosystem and external voice to shape internal change within the institution.

- Going forward a clear post-project strategy that includes long-term funding, ownership structures, and mechanisms for institutional continuity will be important. It will also be important to describe how the pathway fits within the broader frameworks of both UvA Amsterdam UMC and VU, to support wider adoption and sustainability.

AUMC is well positioned to ensure sustainability, particularly through a partnership with its Doctoral School to ensure mandatory trainings for all supervisors in Amsterdam UMC. The establishment of the Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science was accelerated through CATALISI. It has had a strengthening impact and brought both parts of the university closer together. The work positions the University well to advance and lead on the research culture agenda, nationally and internationally. The M-powering responsible supervision course will bring legacy scientific impacts. And the cross-partner initiative during the project, emanating from the Netherlands, and including UCC and UJI in relation to research culture, is a good example of scaled scientific impact.

In summary, the institution achieved deep social and academic impact, as exemplified by the 'MPowering' course, the creation of the Centre for Research Integrity and Open Science Centre Amsterdam (RIOS) and the piloting of the Research Culture survey and, thanks to the AUMC team's strong commitment to the program, we believe that the university is well positioned to achieve long-term and impactful institutional change into the foreseeable future.

3.2. SUMMATIVE EVALUATION RESULTS

As described in Section 2.3.4, UCC conducted a comprehensive **self-evaluation survey in June 2025** with the purpose of also assessing key aspects of the CATALISI project to inform the ongoing and future development of the CATALISI initiative. The findings will be discussed fully in the concluding chapter, where we will delineate key learnings from the formative and summative components. The assessment exercise was successful in providing real time monitoring and evaluation feedback, as well as providing evidence for CATALISI policy and practice recommendations. The topics which were self-assessed by the partners included the items below, which we will analyse in the proceeding sections:

- Action plan implementation.
- Key achievements to date obtained by the facilitating and implementing partners.
- Embedding of the action plans within the HEIs.
- Acceleration Services Utilization/Usefulness/Reproducibility/Recommendations.
- Self-Reflection on the CATALISI project by the partners.
- Main learnings from CATALISI.
- Unanticipated opportunities stemming from the projects and their interactions.
- WP5 exploitation and dissemination information useful for F6S.

3.2.1. Action plan implementation

When analysing the responses by the Implementing Partners, it was clear that each HEI had contextualised Action Plans, which produced a wide variety of interventions and combinations of Acceleration Services to allow each institution to pursue its ultimate goals more efficiently.

The interventions conducted by the HEIs can be summarized in a set of recurring thematic groups: promotion of Open Science (OS), Open Access (OA) and Citizen Science (CS), fostering positive Research Culture and strengthening Academic Capacity, Excellence and Proficiency. To one degree or another, all these themes were present in every Action Plan and mirror the three Domains and interventions are covered withing the CATALISI initiative:

1. Research careers and talent support,
2. Research modus operandi.
3. Sustainable research and education.

Several institutions also focused their Action Plans on interventions which matched the specific 14 intervention areas, contained within the domains, such as Open Science, Open Access and Citizen Science, Research Culture, Academic Capacity, Excellence, Capacity and Evaluation, Sustainability in research finance, Staff Mobility, Stakeholder Engagement, Third Mission.

Although the facilitating partners within the CATALISI initiative did not create specific Action Plans for their organizations, their activities can also be compiled in a set of recurring themes which match the roles of the facilitators as per the GA of the project.

- Administrative and organizational support.
- Dissemination and exploitation.
- Guidance and mentoring.
- External stakeholder engagement.

3.2.2. Key Achievements to Date

Part two of the survey asked each organization to list their key achievements in the CATALISI initiative. The answers were structured in such a way as to differentiate between Outputs (*defined as "tangible products, services or results that emerged from your organization. Key aspects being tangible and measurable and resulting directly from your CATALISI activities"*), Outcomes (*defined as "tangible and measurable changes that resulted from the project"*) and Impacts (*defined as "long-term, lasting effects on your institution that the project achieved. Key aspects being long-term, systemic, contributory to a broader context, directed and focused, and, finally, measurable"*).

Outputs

Implementers: The outputs vary greatly according to each partner organization and their respective Action Plan. The outputs were oriented towards the different intervention areas of CATALISI, specifically in promoting Open Science, Open Access for research and Citizen Science, fostering positive research culture and strengthening academic excellence and evaluation. These outputs included events, seminars, training sessions and courses, furthermore, several HEIs employed survey and monitoring tools to evaluate the pre- and post-intervention conditions, finally, other HEIs have revised their institution's strategic policies as another major output of the initiative.

Facilitators: administrative/logistical outputs: such as the organization and management of key project events (Mobilisation and Mutual Learning events and Twinings), communication & dissemination activities and the submissions of several deliverables. Facilitator outputs also included the support activities specific to their respective Acceleration Services.

Outcomes

Implementers: As identified by the implementing partners: integration and adoption of their interventions, as listed in their Action Plans, within their institutions with a focus on long-term and strategic change.

Facilitators: The outcomes by the facilitating partners, in the words of one of the responders "enabled seven HEIs to co-design and activate tailored institutional transformation pathways across key domains". The support provided by the Facilitators' outcomes allowed the implementing partners to foster cultural shifts, revise their strategies in their specific domains, support HE institutional change and foster deeper stakeholder engagement – all these with a focus on long-term and strategic integration.

Impacts

Implementers: Overall, in the case of impacts, the HEIs appeared reluctant to explicitly commit to listing impacts as per the definition of the survey. Many answers in this section described activities and changes which were more in line with the definition of Output or Outcome. Although it is clear that the HEIs have made considerable steps in integrating their actions in their institutions, these cannot be considered impacts per-se as the "long-term, lasting effects" are difficult to ascertain at this phase of the initiative. This exposes the well-known limitations in evaluating the impact of a long-term institutional change within the confines of a term-limited initiative, as the monitoring and evaluation for several activities would need to continue well beyond the deadline of the CATALISI initiative in December 2025; this also reflects the ongoing difficulties for several implementing partners in articulating the concept of "impact" and concretely translating it to actions within their institution. That said, many of the listed Outputs and Outcomes can be seen as useful and promising indicators for future long-term sustainability and impact in their respective institutions.

Facilitators: The facilitating partners' responses in this section demonstrated clearly outlined and explicit impacts for their organizations. The Facilitators mentioned the impact of CATALISI in allowing their organizations to understand more clearly how to support and guide HEIs in transformational endeavours. The initiative has allowed the facilitators to understand more deeply the inner workings of HEIs and how the process of institutional transformation can be integrated with their own specific, sectoral expertise. Several facilitators are already considering using the lessons learned through CATALISI to provide further services and support for HEIs in their own contexts beyond the end of the project.

3.2.3. Embedding Actions

The responses in this section demonstrated clear similarities and structure. Firstly, all implementing partners have made strides in ensuring that the activities and changes in their Action Plans were integrated at a strategic level in their institutions. These include integrating Open Science, Open Access and Citizen Science methodologies and Living Labs as main drivers of research and innovation, furthermore, each HEI has put in place measures to ensure long-term sustainability of their interventions, going from the common goals as previously mentioned, to the more HEI-specific objectives as listed in their respective Action Plans. A

clear theme which emerged from these responses is the need to integrate high-level decision-makers in the actions undertaken by the partners, these include at the rector or vice rector office level. In the words of one of the responders:

"The key to achieving institutional change lies precisely in these forms of collaboration and in building trust within the university's key management structures. We believe that, as a standalone project, it would be difficult to introduce meaningful changes unless these bodies support us and unless the project's agenda can be aligned with the university's broader institutional change agenda".

In the case of the facilitating partners, some of the organizations were able to incorporate the lessons learned from CATALISI mostly at a department/office level, with the CATALISI team members learning greatly from the initiative's experiences which will leave these sections better equipped for future initiatives which may involve HEIs. That said, other organizations were also able to integrate some of the actions and activities conducted under CATALISI at a higher, strategic level. As already mentioned previously in this report, several facilitators are already considering future initiatives which can be conducted after the end of CATALISI, which will involve HEIs and one Facilitator is already leveraging its experience gained within CATALISI for another already active European-funded project.

	Implementers	Facilitators	Total
Unit/Department Level	7 (14%)	6 (60%)	13 (22%)
University- /Company-Wide, Strategic Level	42 (86%)	4 (40%)	46 (78%)
Total Actions	49	10	59

TABLE 13: INTEGRATION OF ACTIONS AND ACTIVITIES BY PARTNERS, RESULTS FROM UCC SURVEY.

86% of the activities in the Implementers action plans were integrated at a university-wide, strategic level. This means that in the main, the universities were focused on accelerating university-wide change. 14% of the actions/activities were at the local unit/department-level, whereby those universities piloted and trialled change agendas in their own units in the first instance.

	Implementers	Facilitators	Total
Vice Rector / Vice President for Research	5	1	6 (66%)
Faculty Head	4	1	5 (55%)
Department / Unit Head	6	2	8 (88%)
Line Manager	3	0	3 (33%)
Others	1	0	1 (11%)

TABLE 14:
FOR
PLAN
FROM KEY

SUPPORT
ACTION
ACTIVITIES
ACTORS

IN HEIS, RESULTS FROM UCC SURVEY.

6 out of the 7 Implementers have received support from department heads in conducting their actions and 5 out of 7 received support at a vice-rector/vice-president level.

3.2.4. HEI Self-Reflection on CATALISI

With few exceptions, the implementing partners were satisfied with their respective Action Plans and the activities/obtainments within. What is noteworthy is the presence of relatively few mentions of the CATALISI initiative more broadly in the responses of the Implementers, with the vast majority of the comments mirroring the bullet points of their Action Plans, with few mentions of how the Acceleration Services facilitated these actions. That said, many HEIs mentioned the utility in learning from their other implementing partners and the action of cross-pollination which occurred in communicating with the other HEIs. This can be seen as an implicit praise especially for certain Acceleration Services such as the MMLs and Twinning which allowed the different HEIs to share important knowledge as demonstrated in other sections of this report.

When looking at the facilitating partners, the comments primarily revolved around the CATALISI initiative more broadly and the supporting activities. It is clear from the responses that CATALISI was a new experience for several of these partners, and they leveraged the knowledge gained through the initiative to better equip them for future project and integration with HEIs and academia. The Facilitators were pleased to see the Acceleration Services provide the Implementers with the tools and knowhow to catalyse institutional change.

3.2.5. Learnings from CATALISI

Part 5 of the survey aimed at identifying, from the partner's perspectives, the main learnings from CATALISI on four different levels: their organization/institution, their national HE context, the European Commission (for future policy recommendations etc.), and future "CATALISI-like" initiatives.

Organizational Context Learnings

Implementers: The main learning for the implementing partners within their own institutions revolved around the utility of certain Acceleration Services; the need to "find a balance between an ambitious and a realistic action plan" and the "value of aligning institutional transformation with practical, targeted actions"; the importance of maintaining a strong engagement with external stakeholders throughout the project, with one partner this clearly "produced higher uptake and faster policy change". That said, according to some partners, it is not entirely clear if "CATALISI, as a project, has provided a substantially new methodology or response beyond what was already being explored at institutional level" and that "while the facilitators have made sincere efforts to guide the process, some of the proposed dynamics have felt somewhat disconnected from the practical realities of our institutions". Furthermore, "there has been a lack of coherence in how we report our activities—at times it feels as though the different components of the project are not well integrated".

Facilitators: Almost unanimously, for the facilitating partners, the main learnings within their organizations revolved around gaining a deeper understanding and appreciation for complex nature of institutional change within higher education. Every facilitator underlined the initial difficulty in aligning their own specific experience with that of their HEI partners. That said, the facilitators learned how to better adapt their knowhow and services toward academic partners. Furthermore, as another lesson

learned thanks to the initiative, they all mentioned the acknowledgement of how deeply cultural the task of institutional change is within HEIs, underlining that “cultural shifts demand time, commitment, trust, and shared language, which CATALISI helped nurture”.

National HE Context Learnings

The responses in this section mirror the diverse set of national HE environments which each implementing partner occupies. One clear theme in the responses was the necessity and utility of CATALISI in streamlining and helping universities explore new income streams in a period of strong budgetary uncertainty when it comes to research funding in HE. The need to economize, strengthen efficiency and pursue “targeted funding schemes that support long-term, structural change within HEIs”.

“At the national level, CATALISI highlights the critical importance of policy support and dedicated funding mechanisms to drive and sustain institutional transformation within Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)” and that “while each HEI operated within distinct national policies, funding mechanisms, and governance structures, many faced similar barriers in advancing institutional transformation”.

CATALISI also helped in underlining the need to integrate QH stakeholders in universities’ decision-making processes. To put it in one of the responder’s words: “Another key learning was the varying levels of readiness across national contexts to support participatory approaches in institutional change”. Finally, several partners underlined the differences between the national HE contexts facing each institution with “the project reveals a gap in national frameworks for formally recognizing non-traditional learning and engagement”.

European Commission Context Learnings and “future CATALISI” initiatives

The proposals and observations towards the EC and future CATALISI initiatives were many and diverse. Given their variety and the insightful comments, it has been decided to let the partners “speak for themselves”. Below is a selection of direct quotes and insights made by the facilitating and implementing partners, anonymized for the purposes of this report.

CATALISI and funding:

- *The need for “streamlining and exploring new funding streams” and the “difficulties presented by the fact that each member state has different policies and regulations regarding HE which poses issues in implementing overarching solutions for institutional change”.*
- *“The EC might also consider ways to facilitate long-term sustainability of these efforts by linking such initiatives with other EU funding schemes or policy instruments, ensuring greater integration and continuity beyond project duration”.*

CATALISI’s structure:

- *“Future calls should include provisions to ensure sustainability of results and change over time”.*
- *“Given the slow pace of institutional change, projects should span at least 4 years”.*
- *“It would be helpful to better identifying staff members who will work on a similar project. Often, researchers really need to be supported by the governance level (e.g. middle/top managers, administration, technicians)”.*

- *"A key learning from CATALISI is the importance of strategic alignment and institutional coordination across governance, faculty, and administration to achieve long-term transformation".*

Action Plans and Acceleration Services:

- *Priority must be given in "identifying streamlined but highly impactful action plans" and "there is a need to clarify and align definitions, especially regarding "acceleration services." It is also important to identify the most prominent and specific areas for institutional transformation early in the process".*
- *The partners would have "preferred more explanation/application of acceleration services, e.g. practical guidance on the theory of change".*
- *"The MML events worked very well, especially thanks to the in-person nature of the event" while the "twinning events could be conducted fully online".*
- *"Questions emerged on the utility of both a Transformational Pathway and Action Plan, one might be enough for future initiatives".*
- *"Design for scalability by requiring each action to produce a "template" that other institutions can lift verbatim. Build adaptive timelines: corporate cycles, academic semesters and policy windows rarely align, so include contingency buffers up front".*

CATALISI and external stakeholders:

- *"Co-design from day one: early and continuous co-creation with HEIs and stakeholders ensures that tools like digital platforms, communication strategies, and acceleration services are grounded in real institutional needs. This approach fosters ownership, usability, and long-term relevance".*
- *"The project also showed that institutional transformation is most effective when it is embedded in the broader quadruple helix ecosystem, connecting academia with industry, government, and civil society. This reinforces the importance of promoting cross-sector collaboration and multi-stakeholder innovation ecosystems as part of the European Research and Higher Education Area goals".*
- *"Cross-functional collaboration drives innovation: The success of CATALISI was rooted in strong collaboration across technical, academic, and policy domains. Future projects should foster interdisciplinary teams and create mechanisms for continuous knowledge exchange between partners".*

3.2.6. Unanticipated Opportunities

The partners were asked to share and describe any unanticipated activities, synergies or strategic collaborations which emerged as a result of the CATALISI initiative, which were not expected initially. Given the anonymized nature of this report, specific details of the responses will not be shared. That said, several reoccurring themes can be identified in the answers.

- Collaborations between the members were co-created as spontaneous outgrowths of conversations between the partners such as a joint survey which will be conducted by three implementing partners on Research Culture and Ethics within their institutions.
- New research income streams were identified for funding during the exchanges between the partners.

- Research Grants leaning on the CATALISI methodology were successfully obtained by partners which were not initially planned.
- Cooperations with QH stakeholders which were not known at the beginning of the CATALISI initiative.
- Several partners were put in contact with, and participated in events and conferences, which they were not aware of when the initiative was commenced.
- More broadly, the facilitating partners mentioned how the initiative allowed them to experience and begin to grasp the hitherto unexpected and unknown peculiarities of the internal workings of HEIs. This underlines another great obtainment of CATALISI, which was the opportunity for the Facilitators to gain a more profound understanding of HEIs and align their "work with broader European Higher Education policy agendas". This has positioned the Facilitators "as a potential partner[s] for future EU-level actions focused on systemic institutional change".

3.2.7. Exploitation and Dissemination

The purpose of this section of the survey was identifying exploitation potential in the outputs and outcomes of the partner's activities with CATALISI. Furthermore, by asking the responders to think and outline their exploitable results, it was hoped that the partners could use this opportunity to further ideate and structure their potential Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Finally, this section of the survey was also envisioned as a further instrument to aid in F6S' work as the lead for WP5. The anonymized results of this section were fed directly to F6S to help in their work.

3.2.8. Acceleration Services

This section of the survey was used to assess the utilization, usefulness and reproducibility of the Acceleration Services utilized throughout the project through the use qualitative, open questions and answers, and quantitative, numerical self-assessments by part of the partners.

- **Living Labs:** Overall, the responses displayed a positive view towards the Living Lab methodology. Although some partners were initially somewhat sceptical towards employing this service, they all expressed their appreciation towards LL methodologies and their applicability in HE. Most of the recommendations revolved around administrative aspects to ensure long-term sustainability and effectiveness.
- **Counselling:** The comments on the Counselling Acceleration Service were quite diverse with both positive remarks made about the utility of the service but also a wide range of suggestions and constructive feedback on how to improve it, especially in defining and explaining more concretely how this service was conceptualized and created to help the Implementers. A recurring comment revolved around the apparent lack of understanding by the implementing partners as to the exact function of this Acceleration Service. The fact that several partners are still asking this question in the final phase of the project is noteworthy.
- **Transformational Pathway:** Firstly, what is worth noting is the fact that only half of the responders had comments to make in relation the Transformational Pathway. That said, most of the comments were about the need to embed the Transformational Pathways at a high-strategic level within universities, identifying clear and impactful goals, and the need to involve university management in their design. These suggestions, in combination with the relatively low number of comments made in this section (which could either be explained by a low understanding, or interest, towards this service) does raise the question as to whether the overlap between the Action

Plan and Transformational Pathway is such as to warrant the existence of both as separate aspect of the CATALISI initiative.

- **Predictive Studies on Skill Anticipation:** The primary comment in this section revolved around the need to ensure that the results and findings of this Acceleration Service are shared with the HEIs and translated into practical guidance and strategy. It must also be pointed out that the webinar conducted by EY on the findings of the study was the most attended webinar of the CATALISI catalogue of webinars, highlighting the focus that European universities are placing on skills development and forecasting.
- **Community of Practice:** Also in the case of the CoP, several partners noted the relative lack of utility in this Acceleration Service with one comment in particular noting the need to “clarify the role and added value of the CoP for its members”. Other responses underlined the need to ensure that the participants of the CoP are aligned, as having common and possessing “specific shared interest” is more important for the long-term sustainability of a CoP than “broad outreach” and a sheer volume of adherents.
- **Reinforce Human Capital:** The comments and suggestions by the partners in relation to the Reinforce Human Capital were numerous and exhaustive. Overall, per CATALISI partners, this service is potentially the most powerful and useful within the project, which is mirrored by the largely positive responses and the engaged feedback made to improve it. A need for increased flexibility in the way the MMLs and Twinning exchanges were organized was underlined by several partners. In particular, allowing for more hybrid or online participation, without a requirement for in-person attendance, especially in the case of the Twinning, was noted in the comments. Ensuring a wider range of participants, including external QH stakeholders and high-level university administrators was also suggested, as this would allow for maximized results, ensuring greater dedicated resources for the discussions and outputs which stemmed from said discussions, and aid in embedding both the MML/Twinning methodologies, as well as the broader goals and tools of CATALISI, within the universities at a strategic level. Finally, ensuring that the partners are well prepared before participating in the MMLs and Twinning to maximise the utility of the discussions, scheduling the events well in advance compared to how they were in CATALISI, and providing more language flexibility for partners which aren't as accustomed to English as other, were all suggested as small changes which could further boost this Accelerations Service's strengths.
- **Catalyst Hub:** Just as with other previously mentioned Acceleration Services, the Catalyst Hub (formerly the CATALISI Marketplace) had very few comments or suggestions in relation to its utility and ways to improve it. This mirrors the relatively lacklustre responses in this report. The concepts of commercialization and marketability seem to be quite foreign for the HEIs, and the Catalyst Hub has struggled both in helping the Implementers better comprehend the potential and exploitability of their outputs and results, as well as concept as a whole.

Tables on Acceleration Services

The tables below describe scores, between 0 and 10, by the partners on each Acceleration Service. While the detailed data is presented here, for the purpose of commentary, we have used the average scores. The scores are as follows: emerging (0 to 3), intermediate (4 to 7), advanced (8 to 10).

Acceleration Services Utilization

	Implementers			Facilitators			Total		Median Spread
	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	
Living Lab	8.3	8	7, 10	7	9	2, 10	7.9	8	-1
Counselling	5.1	5	3, 7	3.6	3	3, 5	4.6	5	+2
Transformational Pathway	6.1	5.5	4, 9	7.3	7	6, 9	6.5	6	-1.5
Predictive Studies on Skill Anticipation	5	5.5	0, 8	5.3	5	4, 7	5.1	5	+0.5
Community of Practice	5	5	2, 7	8.3	8	8, 9	6.1	6	-3
Capacity Building and Outreach	5.1	6	0, 8	9.3	10	8, 10	6.5	8	-4
Catalyst Hub	3.3	3.5	0, 7	8.3	8	7, 10	5	5	-4.5
Average Between Acc. Services' Median	5.5			7.1			6.1		Average Spread: -1.6

TABLE 15: UTILIZATION OF EACH CATALISI ACCELERATION SERVICES AS RATED BY THE PARTNERS FROM 0 TO 10. EMERGING (0 TO 3), INTERMEDIATE (4 TO 7), ADVANCED (8 TO 10).

The Living Lab service was the most engaged with by the Implementers and the one deemed to be the most utilized, with the Capacity Building and Outreach as second. Every other service was rated as underutilized, with a mark below 6-out-of-10. The average engagement was 5.5. In the case of the Implementers, utilization and engagement with the services was overall considerably higher with the Capacity Building and Outreach and Living Labs being the highest marking. That said, most of the services received higher marks with the Facilitators, with an average of 7.1.

The total spread indicates a higher level of optimism in the engagement and utilization of the services by the Facilitators.

Acceleration Services Usefulness

	Implementers			Facilitators			Total		Median Spread
	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	
Living Lab	8.4	9	4, 10	9.5	9.5	9, 10	8.6	9	-0.5

Counselling	6	7	2, 9	4.5	4.5	4, 5	5.6	5	+2.5
Transformational Pathway	7	7.5	4, 9	8.5	8.5	8, 9	7.3	8	-1
Predictive Studies on Skill Anticipation	5	5.5	0, 9	5.5	5.5	5, 6	5.1	5.5	0
Community of Practice	5.3	5	1, 9	7.5	7.5	6, 9	5.7	6	-2.5
Capacity Building and Outreach	5.8	6	0, 9	10	10	10, 10	6.8	7.5	-4
Catalyst Hub	4.3	5	0, 9	7	7	6, 10	4.8	6	-2
Average Between Acc. Services' Median	6.4			7.5			6.7		Average Spread -1.0

TABLE 16: USEFULNESS OF THE ACCELERATION SERVICES TOWARDS SUPPORTING THE PARTNER'S DELIVERY OF PLANNED ACTIVITIES THROUGH THE CATALISI INITIATIVE. AS RATED BY THE PARTNERS FROM 0 TO 10. EMERGING (0 TO 3), INTERMEDIATE (4 TO 7), ADVANCED (8 TO 10).

When it comes to the usefulness, Implementers and Facilitators displayed a closer alignment in their responses, with the former averaging a 6.4 and the latter a 7.5, demonstrating a higher level of agreement on the usefulness of the services and their potential. That said, there seemed to be some misalignment on which services were more useful than others.

Acceleration Services Reproducibility

	Implementers			Facilitators			Total		Median Spread
	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	
Living Lab	7.1	8	0, 10	9	9	9, 10	7.5	8	-1
Counselling	5.3	7	0, 10	6	6	5, 7	5.4	7	+1
Transformational Pathway	5.7	6	0, 10	7	7	7, 7	6	7	-1
Predictive Studies on Skill Anticipation	4	3	0, 8	5	5	5, 5	4.2	5	-2
Community of Practice	5.8	7	0, 9	8.3	8	8, 9	6.6	8	-1
Capacity Building and Outreach	5.6	8	0, 8	9.5	9.5	9, 10	6.4	8	-1.5
Catalyst Hub	4	3	0, 8	8.3	9	6, 10	5.3	5.5	-6

Average Between Acc. Services' Median	6	7.6	6.9	Average Spread: -1.6
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TABLE 17: ACCELERATION SERVICES REPRODUCIBILITY, CONFIDENCE OF PARTNERS IN REUSING ACCELERATION SERVICES TO SUPPORT ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE GOING FORWARD. AS RATED BY THE PARTNERS FROM 0 TO 10. EMERGING (0 TO 3), INTERMEDIATE (4 TO 7), ADVANCED (8 TO 10).

Also, in the case of the reproducibility of the services, the Facilitators demonstrated a higher level of optimism with a 7.6 average mark compared to the 6 given by the Implementers. That said, both the Living Lab and Capacity Building displayed very high marks for all partners, followed by the Community of Practice and Counselling. The greatest mismatch was with the Catalyst Hub, with the Implementers considering the service much less reproducible than the Facilitators.

4. CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

As referenced in D.4.1, theoretical insights (Kezar and Holcombe 2019), and evidence from the CATALISI project itself, guide us towards a nuanced and expansive theory of organisational change underpinning CATALISI.

Firstly, Systems Theory (ref) and Network Theory (Rogers, 2003; Tenkasi & Chesmore, 2003) allows us to view CATALISI domains and acceleration services as linked, interrelated and mutually reinforcing.

CATALISI as a network created the informational channels for organisational change ideas to flow, for HEI's to innovate as a community, cross networking their intellectual capital and knowledge about how to implement change. It provides an environment to rigorously test the efficacy of the CATALISI model. Importantly, the CATALISI structured process of accelerating learning builds resiliency of institutions and inter-institutionally across regions, a key goal of WIDERA.

Moreover, CATALISI's focus on inter-institutional networking through services such as Living Labs, MML's, Twinning and a Community of Practice offer a practical set of mechanisms that enable change through well organised communication systems, knowledge transfer processes, alteration of schema /mind-sets and shaping of attitudes, increasing of problem solving, and accountability; and especially enhancing learning and social capital, such as risk-taking that can be less problematic if it is done collectively across HEI's rather than individually.

Critically, the CATALISI model emphasizes societal engagement and the role of external Quadruple Helix (QH) partners in co-producing HEI change processes. The societal voice is an important stakeholder, especially as a mechanism to expand democratic knowledge production within universities. Indeed, involving stakeholders across the QH can lead to resilient decision making and stronger outcomes. CATALISI has demonstrated that using new governance modalities in the change process helps to strategically embed the change post project. Co-design ensures that the voices of diverse stakeholders—academic staff, external partners, and civil society are integrated into the planning and implementation of change. This approach fosters ownership, relevance, and sustainability of the HEI transformation actions. Below are a few comments from CATALISI partners on the importance of QH engagement:

- *“Co-design from day one: early and continuous co-creation with HEIs and stakeholders ... fosters ownership, usability, and long-term relevance”.*
- *“...connecting academia with industry, government, and civil society. This reinforces the importance of promoting cross-sector collaboration and multi-stakeholder innovation ecosystems as part of the European Research and Higher Education Area goals”.*
- *“Cross-functional collaboration drives innovation: The success of CATALISI was rooted in strong collaboration across technical, academic, and policy domains. Future projects should foster interdisciplinary teams and create mechanisms for continuous knowledge exchange between partners”.*

Secondly, Organizational Learning Theory (Argyris & Schön, 1996; Kezar, 2005) allows us to see CATALISI as an exemplar effort at scaling HEI change through accelerated co-learning:

- CATALISI focuses on the provision of the acceleration services that need to be in place to support organizational learning such as co-design, monitoring and evaluation, and practices for fostering learning such as Counselling, Mentoring, MML, Twinning and Community of Practice, etc. It therefore helps create knowledge, and the

leadership and culture required to ensure that the new knowledge is embedded and organizational learning occurs.

- The evidence from CATALISI demonstrates that collaboration and mutual learning among institutions accelerates innovation and helps avoid common pitfalls. Sharing experiences and best practices fosters collective intelligence and strengthens transformation efforts. The model positions universities as agents of their own internal change processes through peer-to-peer learning and practitioner-driven change.
- Pursuing change through ideating, co-creating, acting, and adjusting through ongoing monitoring and evaluation is not the norm in large organisations such as HEI's, and requires a mind-set change. Important in CATALISI is the ways in which individuals within the HEI's worked to understand these concepts and found ways to sustain learning by embedding them into their organizational structures. For CATALISI HEIs this required a willingness to experiment and learn through doing, especially in the case of Living Labs. Using the acceleration services as appropriate and embedding these within action plans worked well but this involved the effective use of a Theory of Change and strategic KPIs (and having clear ownership of the actions within plans), again shifting the HEI's towards evidence informed planning and decision making.
- CATALISI's organizational learning framework allowed for and encouraged capitalizing on new opportunities for collaboration as they emerged during the initiative. This included collaboration on funding streams, Citizen Science initiatives, and a joint survey conducted by three implementing partners on Research Culture and Ethics within their institutions. These developments underscore the potential of the initiative to generate lasting value beyond its formal scope.
- However, to strengthen knowledge-sharing and collaborative learning, future projects should reduce the number of domains and intervention areas addressed, ensuring that the number of intervention areas is fewer than the number of implementing partners. This approach will encourage overlap in the selection of focus areas, enabling partners to learn from each other and undertake transformation journeys together, rather than each focusing on a separate topic. Overlapping domains foster the exchange of best practices and collective problem-solving, leading to more robust and adaptable solutions. It also supports the development of replicable models that can be scaled across institutions, enhancing the overall impact and sustainability of transformation efforts. Future iterations on the use of the CATALISI model could explore the potential of having 'coupled' leading and following partners. By working together on shared challenges, partners could build stronger networks and accelerate progress toward common goals.
- The Theory of Change approach is an important component of organisational learning. Its Impact focus, formative and summative modalities with a layering of strategic KPI and feedback loops enables adaptive management and continuous improvement. It introduced an action and reflection nexus that led to strategic KPIs that opened a door to change processes embraced by HEI leadership and practitioners. The approach unearthed the 'meaning' beneath indicators, and a qualitative understanding of change and its cascading effect or impact, including the social reach of the initiative. For example, UJI was initially focused on delivering Open Science information events when a Strategic Plan for Open Science was needed. Similarly, AUMC was focused on delivering a course and training on research integrity but subsequently delivered a dedicated Research Centre which helped anchor this activity post-project.

UCC developed structured feedback on the Acceleration Services and found a mixed set of opinions and suggestions. Briefly:

- **Living Labs** were well utilized and generally appreciated, though partners called for greater adaptability and stakeholder involvement.
- **Counselling** services received both praise and criticism, with some partners unclear about their purpose.
- **Transformational Pathways** were seen as useful when endorsed by senior leadership, though overlapping with other planning tools was noted.
- Other services, such as **Predictive Studies** and the **Community of Practice**, were viewed as somewhat less impactful in terms of university change, with suggestions for improved integration and clearer objectives.
- **Capacity Building and Outreach** received positive feedback. Partners valued the opportunity for peer learning and recommended greater flexibility in format, broader stakeholder inclusion, and improved scheduling.
- The **Catalyst Hub** was met with limited engagement, and partners called for clearer purposes and stronger involvement of HEIs.

These summaries which emerged through the formative evaluative processes were corroborated by the main summative evaluative tool, the reflective, self-evaluative survey.

Recommendations for the future of the model included clearer definitions of acceleration services, and possibly a fewer number of these accelerations which each implementer can choose to use during the implementation of their transformational pathway. Differences in readiness and support across national contexts were noted, with some institutions operating in more conducive environments than others.

The feedback from partners was such that there were some acceleration services that were more relevant than others. Therefore, there may be a case for primary (obligatory) and secondary (selective) acceleration services, the latter which could be chosen if applicable to your transformation.

Some partners expressed uncertainty about the purpose and utility of specific support mechanisms, particularly those related to exploitability and commercialization (Catalyst Hub). However, cultural resistance to non-traditional methods such as the Catalyst Hub was also noted, especially in contexts where institutional change is slow or contested.

Successful utilisation of the acceleration services, for example, in-person Twinning exchanges and Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops contributed in a leading way to change especially when these were well planned. Community of Practice events such as online webinars and presentations should be intrinsically linked to relevant action items relevant to the partners. Similarly, advanced impacts and collaboration on change grew organically from in-person exchanges over virtual.

In summary, Acceleration Services such as Living Labs, Design Labs for Transformational Pathways, MML, Twinning, and Counselling provide structured support for institutional change. Their strategic use enables universities to pilot innovations, engage stakeholders, and build capacity in targeted areas. Future projects should streamline the number of acceleration services offered and focus on their practical aspects, simplifying their descriptions and ensuring clarity of purpose. Lessons learned from CATALISI indicate that overly complex or vaguely defined services can hinder implementation, interpretation and uptake among partners. Concentrating on a select set of well-defined services enables deeper engagement and more effective capacity building. Clear and concise service descriptions make it easier for stakeholders to understand, adopt, and measure the impact of each intervention.

Thirdly, institutional theory (DiMaggio & Powell, 2000) allows us to see CATALISI as promoting an empowering and effective discourse of HEI organisational change.

Institutional Theory accounts for new schema or sets of norms, embedded in language, and transferred through discourse. Indeed, the values communicated through discourse underpinning CATALISI are consistent with more ethical and inclusive decision-making processes that involve QH actors and devolve agency to practitioners through co-learning and peer-to-peer exchange. Initiatives such as CATALISI are at risk of being perceived as promoting a managerial or technocratic discourse. However, as opposed to a more neo liberal market model of higher education, CATALISI emphasizes practitioner-academic leadership and strengthening democratic institutions as posited in the EU aims and values as expressed in the Lisbon Treaty and Charter of Fundamental Rights.

Institutional types (Bergquist 2008) such as more collegial or consensus-driven approaches versus more managerial or top-down decision-making environments, require a level of diagnosis, as these shape the context for acceleration services. Where CATALISI is strongest, it is a system to drive institutional culture change. Thus, sensitivity to alignment with institutional values and the ways in which relationships are formed and how things get planned and completed within a HEI are vital considerations. This includes understanding and securing institutional commitments and being aware of readiness levels, and tailoring expectations accordingly. Involving the right people in the change project is vital. The learning in CATALISI shows that a partnership approach with the involvement of senior leadership and decision makers contributed positively to change agendas.

The involvement of senior leadership was identified as a key factor in achieving alignment with broader organizational agendas. In this regard, CATALISI has also highlighted a false dichotomy between so-called top-down and bottom-up approaches. It has demonstrated a far more nuanced view of leadership and what it is in practice. Concepts such as 'Stewardship' and 'Distributed Leadership' are more apt in describing the leadership approaches enabled through CATALISI, as it contributed to a partnership approach and an 'empowering ecosystem' and not simply a top down-bottom-up approach.

"The key to achieving institutional change lies precisely in these forms of collaboration and in building trust within the university's key management structures. We believe that, as a standalone project, it would be difficult to introduce meaningful changes unless these bodies support us and unless the project's agenda can be aligned with the university's broader institutional change agenda".

"A key learning from CATALISI is the importance of strategic alignment and institutional coordination across governance, faculty, and administration to achieve long-term transformation".

Momentum is also a very important aspect. Changes in personnel at implementer level can lead to a loss of momentum when people leave or are replaced. Changing of PIs/PM took place in 5 of the 11 partners. While the model is resilient, in that the project was delivered, and results obtained, momentum (as a concept) is central to change in HEIs and requires consistency of effort and personnel over time.

Regarding Action Plan implementation, most of the partners' actions were integrated at the strategic level, indicating a strong discourse of commitment to embedding change within core institutional structures.

- The interventions conducted by the HEIs can be summarized in a set of recurring thematic groups: promotion of Open Science (OS), Open Access (OA) and Citizen Science (CS), fostering positive Research Culture and strengthening Academic Capacity, Excellence and Proficiency. several institutions also focused their Action Plans on more unique interventions which were more specific to their requirements

such as sustainability in research finance and Stakeholder Engagement, / Third Mission.

- 86% of the activities in the Implementers action plans were integrated at a university-wide, strategic level. This means that in the main, the universities were focused on accelerating university-wide change. 14% of the actions/activities were at the local unit/department-level, whereby those universities piloted and trialled change agendas in their own units in the first instance.
- CATALISI shows that most advanced outcomes are achieved through scaling deep not wide. This means leveraging and adding value to existing university priorities and initiatives. Actions work best when they focus on deepening university efforts in strategic areas. Often the timing is right for a particular change item or focus and CATALISI allowed for that to be accelerated and progressed. The main learning for the implementing partners within their own institutions revolved around the need to “find a balance between an ambitious and a realistic action plan” and the “value of aligning institutional transformation with practical, targeted actions”. The learning from CATALISI is that careful planning is important when starting to define actions and developing indicators that are strategic and not overly operational and lagging.

“Priority must be given to identifying streamlined but highly impactful action plans” and “there is a need to clarify and align definitions, especially regarding “acceleration services.” It is also important to identify the most prominent and specific areas for institutional transformation early in the process”.

- Setting clear priorities enables institutions to concentrate resources and efforts on areas with the highest potential impact. Overly broad or diffuse objectives can dilute effectiveness and hinder progress. Getting the right balance between ambition and realism on what can be achieved during the term of the change project is an important consideration. Some of the most advanced outcomes came from universities that had a relatively narrow focus and appeared to be spending time on the right activity. UCC observed that embedding the actions in strategic documents of the university can also be helpful regarding successful delivery.
- Transformation pathways are dynamic and must evolve in response to feedback, changing priorities, and institutional developments. Iterative planning allows universities to refine their strategies, incorporate evaluations, and remain responsive to internal and external contexts. Ensuring the longevity of transformation initiatives beyond project funding requires early and strategic planning. Sustainability involves embedding new practices into institutional structures, securing resources, and building long-term support.

To be clear, for the universities that were advanced in delivering university-wide change during the project, some common success factors emerged from the formative and summative evaluation process undertaken by UCC:

- **Who:** Involving the right people in the project. A partnership with senior leadership and decision makers contributed positive and strategic change agendas. Involving stakeholders led to more robust decision making. Using existing and new governance structures in the change agenda helps to strategically embed the change post project completion.
- **What:** Getting the right balance between ambition and realism on what can be achieved during the term of the project. The External Acceleration Board also raised this in their feedback to partners, and this was operationalized by UCC throughout

the evaluation process. Some of the most advanced outcomes came from universities that had a relatively narrow focus. Spending time on the right activity.

- **Where:** Successful utilization of the acceleration services. For example, on-site twinning's and mutual learning events contributed in a leading way to change, especially when these were well planned. Online webinars and presentations require linking to relevant action items relevant to the partners. Similarly, advanced impacts and collaboration on change emanated from in-person exchanges. Embedding the actions in strategic documents of the university can also be helpful with regard to delivery.
- **When:** It was clear that some of the most advanced outcomes were delivered through leveraging work that was already commenced in universities and adding value, or through synergies and building on previous projects. The timing was right for those particular areas of focus, and CATALISI allowed that to be accelerated and progressed.
- **How:** Using the acceleration services as appropriate and embedding these within action plans. Pursuing the change through co-creating, implementing, and ongoing evaluation engagement. A move to the use of a Theory of Change and strategic KPIs and having clear ownership of the actions within plans are all common to the universities that were advanced in delivering desired change.

Finally, the process of defining Transformation Pathways and Actions related to core intervention areas and their synchronicity with the formative and summative evaluation approach brought forward considerable results across the Implementers. Fundamental also was the mutual exchange with facilitators, which was key to the whole implementation process through continuous reflection on how to refine Actions to the given situation. The outcomes in the words of one of the partners "*enabled seven HEIs to co-design and activate tailored institutional transformation pathways across key domains*". The support provided by the Facilitators especially allowed the implementing partners to foster cultural shifts, revise their strategies in their specific domains, support timely HE institutional change and foster deeper stakeholder engagement – all these with a focus on long-term and strategic integration.

In conclusion, CATALISI considers institutional transformation in HEIs as a complex process, requiring deep shifts in specified domains encompassing aspects such as governance, culture, research practices, and financial sustainability. The CATALISI methodology supports HEIs in going through this transformation by offering a range of acceleration services designed to accelerate the process and maximize its impact. It is important to note that CATALISI's approach is iterative and adaptive, allowing for continuous learning and improvement. CATALISI's domains and acceleration services are linked, interrelated and mutually reinforcing. It thus provides an international exemplar for scaling HEI change through accelerated co-learning, and an empowering change discourse. The findings offer valuable insights for policymakers seeking to support systemic transformation in higher education and research.

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6. APPENDIX

ANNEX A: INTRODUCTION TO EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT PROCESS TEMPLATE

(The below annex contains the basic template for the introduction presentation to the evaluation and impact assessment methodology and Toc. This can be used as a guideline to how a successful introduction to these concepts can be given to project partners).

Agenda to Evaluation and Impact Assessment Introduction

1. Introduction / Context – Where we are now

(Utilize this section to introduce the partners to the initial conditions and states based on the data baselines and preceding work conducted, including first EAB feedback on intervention drafts).

2. Evaluation & Impact Assessment – Approach

(Introduce the partners to the Evaluation and Impact Assessment approach in broad terms, the major goals of the project, expected outcomes and processes to achieve them).

3. Organizational Change Framework

(Illustrate the theories and concepts behind Organizational Change and Transformations. There should be an emphasis on the difference between policy-/strategic-led transformation and culture-led transformation in an institution; the degree to which one or the other will be used in the program should be discussed and clarified).

4. Evaluation Methodology

Theory of Change

(Explain the concept behind Theory of Change, in-depth analyses of this can be found in Deliverable 4.1 "Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan" of the CATALISI project).

Formative Evaluation – KPIs, Monitoring and Tools

(Illustrate the Formative component of the evaluation: the co-ideation, co-creation and co-development of KPIs, their monitoring and the different tools which will be used to execute the formative process and the practical/administrative elements in organizing such).

Summative Evaluation

(Illustrate the Summative component of the evaluation: the survey or other tool which will be used for the final ex-post assessment, its expected outcomes and findings, and the practical/administrative elements in organizing such).

5. Practicalities, Follow Up & Next Steps

(Expand on the follow-up steps of the process, with a focus on the high-level operational steps for the next steps).

ANNEX B: PARTNER ACTION PLAN BASELINE DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE

Partner (name) Action Plan

Domain: *(What domain has the partner selected?)*

Intervention Area: *(What intervention area has the partner selected?)*

GOAL: *(What goals does the partner wish to achieve?)*

Activity: <i>(Activity A, B, C, etc. name, this table can be reproduced for each activity/action)</i>	
Leader	Person/group which is leading this action/activity
Contributors	<i>What other partners are contributing?</i>
Start Date	<i>When does it start?</i>
End Date	<i>When does it end?</i>
Milestones	<i>What short-/mid-term goalposts are to be expected?</i>
Resources	<i>What resources will be available to achieve the milestones and end goal?</i>
Obstacles	<i>What expected or potentially unexpected obstacles will be encountered?</i>
Mitigation Measures	<i>What mitigation measures will be in place to control said obstacles?</i>
KPIs	<i>What indicators will monitor the action/activity?</i>
Baseline Values	<i>What is the baseline, starting conditions for said KPI?</i>
Target Values	<i>What are the expected values, end conditions for said KPI?</i>

ANNEX C: PARTNER TOC NARRATIVE TEMPLATE

(Each partner is expected to develop this document in a narrative form and as a "living document" which can be constantly updated and integrated with new ideas and findings. It should read as a "story", describing the partner's initial conditions, selected interventions, expected results, issues and other stakeholders with which they will engage).

Partner (name) Theory of Change Narrative

1. Partner's Institutional Context:

The partner should give a relatively lengthy description of their institutional context.

2. Partner's Domain and Intervention Area Selection:

What Domain and Intervention Area did the partner choose? And why?

3. Partner's Expected Outcomes and Impacts:

What does the partner expect from the selection of these interventions? Outcomes? Impacts?

4. SWOT Analysis: *(For each intervention)*

- a. **Strengths:** *(What does the partner "have going for it" in relation to achieving its expected goals?)*
- b. **Weaknesses:** *(What does the partner perceived as its shortcomings in relation to achieving its expected goals?)*
- c. **Opportunities:** *(What does the partner see as potential opportunities in relation to achieving its expected goals?)*
- d. **Threats:** *(What does the partner see as potential threats in relation to achieving its expected goals?)*

5. Quadruple Helix Engagement: *(For each intervention)*

- a. **Academia:** *(Is the partner engaging with stakeholders in academia? Who and why?)*
- b. **Business:** *(Is the partner engaging with stakeholders in the private sector? Who and why?)*
- c. **Public Administration:** *(Is the partner engaging with stakeholders in local, regional, national or EU administration? Who and why?)*
- d. **Civil Society:** *(Is the partner engaging with stakeholders in civil society and/or the general public? Who and why?)*

ANNEX D: THEORY OF CHANGE MONITORING FRAMEWORK

(The table below can be used to better operationalize the ToC Model Components present in each of the partner's interventions by rendering the impacts, assumptions, outcomes, activities, data needed and responsibilities more explicit, rendering their execution clearer and easier to conduct).

Theory of Change Monitoring Framework		Means of Verification				Use of Information	
ToC Model Component	Indicators (including targets)	Data Sources	Frequency of Collection	Responsibility for Collection	Collection Method	Reporting	Presentation
Impact							
<i>Assumptions</i>							
Outcomes							
<i>Assumptions</i>							
Outputs							
<i>Assumptions</i>							
Activities							
<i>Assumptions</i>							
Inputs							
<i>Assumptions</i>							

ANNEX E: STRUCTURED BILATERAL DISCUSSION TEMPLATE

Partner (name) Action Plan and Transformational Pathway Overview

Partner's Updated Action Plan / Transformational Pathway:	<i>Link to Partner's Framework (e.g. Excel sheet).</i>
Date/Time:	<i>Date and time of discussion.</i>
Participants:	<i>People participating in discussion.</i>

Meeting Discussion Points

1. Transformational Pathway, Action Plan and Updated Actions/Activities:

(Capture discussion in this section by listing actions/activities undertaken by the partner and any updates).

2. Potential Support Needed Towards Embedding Actions within your Institution Long-Term:

(Capture discussion in this section by identifying any areas of support needed by the partner from facilitating partners in the project or the evaluation and impact assessment leader).

3. Engagement with Project Tools and Embedding them in your Institutions for Long-Term Implementation and Utilization:

(Capture discussion in this section regarding the tools, for example Acceleration Services, provided by the project and how the partners are utilizing them and embedding them in the institution for post-project replicability and exploitation).

4. Progress Towards Potential Dissemination and Exploitable Results:

(Capture discussion in this section if there are any dissemination activities or exploitable results which need to be achieved for the project).

ANNEX F: EXAMPLE OF WORKSHOP CO-CREATION AND VALIDATION SESSION

Below is an example of a co-creation board, initially produced in-person on a large poster paper and with the use of sticky notes, and then converted into digital form using a Miro Board.

In this concrete example, produced during the CATALISI General Assembly hosted by AUTH in Thessaloniki in January 2025, at the center of the poster there are the 7 Acceleration Services utilized by CATALISI. The partners (Facilitators and Implementers) were guided, thanks to a PowerPoint presentation displayed on a screen in the conference room, through the different steps of the co-creation workshops.

The partners were initially invited to leave a start sticker, corresponding to the color they selected, on the Acceleration Services they most interacted with. Then the partners were asked to leave comments, criticisms, constructive feedback and suggestions for each service, on a sticky note.

The results stemming from the analysis of the above posters (in this case, three were produced by three, roughly 7-person groups) were compiled in an internal workshop report which was shared with the partners (a screenshot of this report is present in Step 2 of the Toolkit in Chapter 2). The report followed the structure below in illustrating the findings of this specific co-creation workshop:

1. Introduction to workshop,
2. Objectives of the workshop,
3. Structure and process,
4. Questions asked to the partners during the session,
5. Results and findings,
6. Conclusions and recommendations.

This annex should be seen as a concrete example in structuring a useful co-creation and validation session. Other variations and methods can also be used as long as they are able to capture the information needed, as per the internal workshop report.

ANNEX G: EXAMPLE OF INITIAL ACTION PLAN AND KPI MONITORING TOOL

(Below is a blank template of the monitoring tool/sheet for the partner's Action Plans and KPI selection).

“Partner Name”: Action Plan Progress						
Domains and Intervention Areas:						
Activity	Indicators	Target value	Latest value	Status	Notes	Acceleration Service
Activity A	Description of Indicator for Activity A	1	1	Completed		LL, Counselling,
Activity B	Description of Indicator for Activity B	3	3	Completed		LL, Capacity Building, CoP,
Activity C	Description of Indicator for Activity C	3	1	In progress		LL, MML, Counselling,
Activity D	Description of Indicator for Activity D	5	0	To be initiated		Living Lab

ANNEX H: EXAMPLE OF SUMMATIVE SELF-EVALUATION SURVEY

(Below is a concrete example of a Summative Self-Evaluation Survey to be conducted Ex-Post to evaluate the outcome of a project. This specific survey was conducted by UCC in June 2025, towards the end of the CATALISI project and can be used as a template for other assessments).

CATALISI Summative Self-Evaluation Survey by UCC

As part of UCC's WP4 Evaluation and Impact Assessment activities, this survey was conceived as a tool to supplement the summative and formative component of WP4. The survey (which supports the summative evaluation) follows on from the Round 1 Formative Evaluation and the Round 2 Bilateral Meetings conducted between UCC and the CATALISI Implementing Partners in April-May 2025. This formative component of the Evaluation & Impact Assessment is aligned with the ToC and strategic plan KPIs as set out in the Deliverable 4.1 and included as part of UCC's WP4 tasks.

- **Both Facilitators and Implementors** are invited to complete the survey.
- For the purposes of conciseness, **we kindly request that only one survey form is completed per organization.**
- The results of the survey will be kept anonymous, and the ownership of the responses will be known solely to the UCC evaluation team.
- The anonymized outputs of the survey will be shared with the CATALISI partners and inform the next phase of the CATALISI project and possible "post-CATALISI" initiatives. It will also be shared with the External Advisory Board, in summary format, for comments.
- Importantly, the outputs will inform the Policy Recommendation stemming from the project.
- The survey and the evidence collected through the summative and formative evaluation aligns with the ethos of the ERA Policy Agenda 2025-28.
- The survey also aligns with the ethos of CATALISI to Explore, Co-Design, Implement & Evaluate.

Initial description of survey and functions

1. What organization are you responding on behalf of?

APRE

AUTH

ENOLL

EY

F6S

KTU

LUISS

UCC

UG

UII

VUMC

2. What role does your institution fulfil in CATALISI?

Facilitator

Implementer

3. With regard to your role in CATALISI, briefly describe your primary activities. (max 100 words)

Enter your answer

4. In your estimation, what proportion of your action plan (or planned activity, in the case of Facilitators) has been implemented?

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

0%100%

Basic data collection for cataloguing purposes.

Action Plan

5. Please, in bullet-points, list the actions/activities in your action plan in summary format.

Enter your answer

6. For each action/activity, in the order in which you listed them in the previous question, please indicate its progression status

	Planned (not yet commenced)	In Progress	Completed
Action/Activity 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 6	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 7	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 8	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Please categorise your actions (i.e. state whether these are relevant to your department/unit level only or at the university-wide/strategic level).

	Unit/Department Level	University-/Company-Wide, Strategic Level
Action/Activity 1	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 3	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 4	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 5	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 6	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 7	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Action/Activity 8	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Outlining actions and activities undertaken by partner and level of integration in institution.

Key Achievements To Date

Please list your key achievements under the following categories:

8. **Outputs** (i.e. the tangible products, services or results that emerged from your organization. Key aspects being tangible and measurable and resulting directly from your CATALISI activities). (max 100 words)

Enter your answer

9. **Outcomes** (i.e. the tangible and measurable changes that resulted from the project). (max 100 words)

Enter your answer

10. **Impact** (i.e. the long-term, lasting effects on your institution that the project achieved. Key aspects being long-term, systemic, contributory to a broader context, directed and focused, and, finally, measurable). (max 100 words)

Enter your answer

Achievements to date by partner as categorized by output, outcome and impact.

Embedding the Action Plans

11. To date, in your organisation, has the delivery of your actions become embedded or had an impact at the unit-level/faculty-level or on a wider organisational/strategic level? (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

12. At what level did your organisation support your actions/activities?

Vice Rector / Vice President for Research

Faculty Head

Department / Unit Head

Line Manager

Other

Level of embedding actions in institution.

Self-Reflection

13. Which of your achievements are you most proud of? And why? (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

14. Please provide a reflective self-assessment on the implementation of your action plan or delivery of your acceleration service/work package. (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

Self-reflection on the partner's experience in the program.

Learning from CATALISI

From your organisation's perspective, what are the main learnings from CATALISI for:

15. Your organisation (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

16. National HE Context (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

17. The European Commission (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

18. For a future "CATALISI-like" initiative (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

Major learnings for the partner at different levels of analysis.

Unanticipated Opportunities

19. Please list and describe any unanticipated activities, synergies or strategic collaborations which emerged for your organisation as a result of the CATALISI initiative. (max 250 words)

Enter your answer

Opportunities which emerged from the program which were not initially envisioned.

WP5 Exploitation and Dissemination

Please list your main:

20. Dissemination and communication activities, including tangible outputs from these activities. (max 100 words)

Enter your answer

21. Exploitable Results (Key and Other) planned or achieved. (max 100 words)

Enter your answer

Element of the survey which was conceived as an adjunct/help for F6S as WP5 leader.

Acceleration Services Utilization

Please rate the level of your organisations engagement with each of the CATALISI Acceleration Services. Emerging (0 to 3), Intermediate (4 to 7), Advanced (8 to 10)

22. Living Labs:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

23. Counselling:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

24. Transformational Pathways:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

25. Predictive Studies on Skill Anticipation:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

26. Community of Practice:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

27. Capacity Building and Outreach:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

28. Catalyst Hub:

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Low											High

Acceleration Services utilization. This section was reproduced in the survey also for usefulness, reproducibility and general comments.

ANNEX I: EXAMPLE OF GDPR-COMPLIANT MODEL CONSENT FORM TEMPLATE

Below is a generic GDPR-compliant model consent form example to be shared at the beginning of a survey and/or interview to confirm the authorization of use of collected data.

***The form below should be seen as an example and not necessarily exhaustive of all the legal requirements for a complete consent form. Please consult your respective institution's legal and/or ethics department for comprehensive guidance on this approach. ***

Example of GDPR-Compliant Consent Form

Project and Activity Title: *Title of the survey, study, interview, etc.*

Organization Name: *Name of the organization which is conducting the activity.*

DPO (Data Protection Officer) Details: *Details of the person managing the data.*

Purpose of Study: *Use this section to explain for what purposes/reasons the data is being collected.*

Lawful Basis as per GDPR Art. 6: *If the data is being used for purposes of consent, public interest, scientific research, legitimate interest, etc.*

Study Components: *How the activity is structured (format, duration, questions, topics, etc.).*

Data Collected: *What data will be collected.*

Data Use: *How the data will be managed, stored, deleted, etc.*

Data Owner Rights as per GDPR Art. 6: *What rights the data owner possesses (right to access, rectify, erase, restrict, object, withdraw consent, lodge a complaint, etc.).*

Explicit Consent of Participant: *Use this section to get an explicit consent from the participant through the use of a name, signature, date and tick box.*

ANNEX L: LOGIC MODEL TEMPLATE

(Below is a simplified Logic Model Diagram Template which can be used to more clearly map and track the planned interventions, and expected Inputs, Activities, Outputs, Outcomes and Impacts using a Theory of Change Model. Other versions, also in graph or digital-tool form can be used equally effectively).

Input	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text Here • Text Here • Text Here 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text Here • Text Here • Text Here 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text Here • Text Here • Text Here 	Short-Term <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text Here • Text Here • Text Here 	Mid-Term <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text Here • Text Here • Text Here
			Impacts	
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text Here • Text Here • Text Here 	